

SUPERSHINE

D1.3 Engagement for Social Housing refurbishment – Part 1

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Project Acronym	SUPERSHINE
Project Title	S=Smart U=Upgraded asset-values and quality of life P=Public Private Partnership E=Extended Energy Efficiency R=Renewables triggered by the project SH=Social Housing I=Investment N=Net Zero E=European
Project Duration	November 2022– Marh 2026 (41 months)
Deliverable No.	D1.3 - Engagement for Social Housing Refurbishment – Part 1.
Dissemination level	PU
Work Package	WP 1 – Stakeholders’ and residents’ engagement, co-design and social innovation
Task	T1.4 – Engagement Implementation
Lead beneficiary	APRE
Contributing beneficiary/ies	ICONS, ATER, REA, FB
Due date of deliverable	31 December 2024
Actual submission date	31 December 2024

v	Date	Beneficiaries	Trach changes
1.0	30/11/2024	APRE, ICONS, FB, ATER, REA	Draft completion with LH contributions
1.1	10/12/2024	APRE, ICONS	Second draft
2.0	20/12/2024	APRE, ICONS	Third draft
2.1	30/12/2024	APRE, UoY	Review by the SC and the PC and final version

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
ESCO	Energy Service Companies
FVG	Friuli-Venezia Giulia Region
GA	General Assembly
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LH	Lighthouse
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PV	Photovoltaic
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
QoL	Quality of Life
SHC	Social Housing Company
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
UTAUT	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology
SUPERSHINE Partner Acronym	Full name and Description
APRE	Agency for the Promotion of the European Research
ATER	Agency for Public Social Housing of Trieste
AYMING	AYMING Strategic Consultancy Company
BL	BOLIGSELSKABERNES LANDSFORENING – Danish National Association of Housing Companies
CARTIF	Fundacion CARTIF
CIRCE	Foundation Center for Research on Energy Resources and Consumption
DEMIR	DEMIR Enerji
EEIP	Energy Efficiency in Industrial Processes ASBL
EGC	European Green Cities
ENA	Agency for Environment and Energy of Arrábida
FB	FAELLESBO SHC
HE	Housing Europe - European Federation of Public, Cooperative & Social Housing
ICONS	ICONS Foundation
INSME	International Network of Small and Medium Enterprises
KM	Municipality of Kadikoy
REA	Riga Municipality Energy Agency
SPT	SPACETIME Beograd LLC
TENDER	Tendercapital Alternative Funds Plc
UoY	University of York
ZV	Zaragoza Vivienda - Public Agency for Zaragoza Housing

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the output of Task 1.4, where the SUPERSHINE project implemented its engagement strategies for community-led co-design and co-decision processes, developed by ICONS. Implemented across the three SUPERSHINE Lighthouses in Riga, Herning, and Trieste, the project aligned with the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principle “Together,” focusing on inclusive district renovations, with each site at different stages of completion by the end of 2024. The SUPERSHINE engagement process aims at empowering communities to co-create sustainable and aesthetically appealing neighbourhoods, while preserving cultural heritage as well. Supported by APRE, lighthouse managers exchanged innovative solutions, blending environmental, economic, and cultural considerations to meet NEB principles of sustainability and beauty. SUPERSHINE also participated actively in the NEB Community and NEB Lab to advance a human-centred and sustainable built environment.

Baseline data collection for Social Acceptance KPIs evaluated the impact of interventions on residents' awareness, ownership, and satisfaction, while engagement indicators measured the strategy's effectiveness, highlighting areas for improvement in the second part of engagement activities, to be held in 2025. Activities up to date included inclusive initiatives targeting diverse groups, from young people to marginalised communities, supported by facilitators and digital platforms to ensure widespread participation. Localised meetings and accessible materials bridged language and mobility barriers, fostering content ownership. SUPERSHINE emphasised the importance of holistic approaches in social housing refurbishment, combining technical, social, and cultural strategies: key takeaways highlight the transformative power of resident participation, unleashed by SUPERSHINE through reinforcing the role of existing social structure (e.g., the Danish “tenant democracy”) and of digital tools to overcome physical barriers (e.g., Riga’s Tandeems platform), as well as by integrating cultural heritage, social cohesion, and stakeholder collaboration across the energy-efficient renovation value chain, like in the Trieste case. Lessons from the project offer a scalable framework for similar European neighbourhoods, districts, and cities (starting from the SUPERSHINE fellow cities of Belgrade, Zaragoza, Setúbal, and Istanbul), ensuring impactful and co-created community-centred solutions.

1. Introduction

The SUPERSHINE project aims at transforming social housing through stakeholder engagement, energy-efficient renovations, and community-driven co-creation processes, aligning with the principles of sustainability, inclusivity, and aesthetics advocated by the New European Bauhaus (NEB).

The levels of citizen participation. Poster by Christophe Gouache – Strategic Design Scenarios, adapted from ‘Ladder of Participation’ (Arnstein, 1969)

This deliverable is the output of Task 1.4 of the SUPERSHINE project, dedicated to the engagement implementation, testing and fine-tuning the SUPERSHINE social acceptance model developed by ICONS. This innovative methodology promotes awareness and acceptance through community-led co-design and co-decision processes: up to the end of 2024, the community engagement strategy within the three SUPERSHINE Lighthouse sites is actively being implemented in alignment with the New European Bauhaus (NEB) compass pillar “Together”. Recognising the unique context of each lighthouse, the

engagement is unfolding along distinct timelines, with progress tailored to fit the roadmap and milestones specific to each location. This phased approach ensures that community involvement evolves organically, respecting local dynamics and fostering inclusive participation at each stage of development.

The engagement vision of SUPERSHINE aimed at fostering co-creation, vision co-design and co-decision processes, empowering communities to lead the district renovation efforts in their neighbourhoods. Supported by APRE, the lighthouse managers maintained ongoing communication, exchanging innovative solutions and best practices, both technical and socially impactful, rooted in insights from European research and innovation. This collaborative approach sought to fulfil the NEB principles of “Sustainable”, integrating both environmental and economic dimensions, and “Beautiful”, balancing aesthetic appeal with respect for culturally and historically significant architecture, while ensuring practical functionality. These efforts aim at contributing to the creation of NEB-inspired living ecosystems across Europe.

By actively participating in the NEB Community, particularly through the NEB Lab (i.e. the space for co-creation and sharing between NEB projects aimed at making their results more tangible), the lighthouses exchanged practices and expertise aimed at cultivating a more sustainable and human-centred built environment. The task also carried out the baseline data collection for the Social Acceptance KPIs, to measure the impact of SUPERSHINE interventions on residents, both in terms of sense of awareness and acceptability, but also of sense of ownership. These metrics evaluate

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how well the renovations address residents' needs and measure changes in attitudes, sense of belonging, and overall satisfaction. In turn, this data informs an assessment of the social desirability and long-term well-being resulting from the renovations. Additionally, Social Engagement indicators were monitored, with reference to the activities already performed, to gauge the effectiveness of the engagement strategy itself, highlighting areas for future improvement.

Activities included targeted engagement with diverse population groups, such as young people, older adults, and marginalised communities, supported by on-site facilitators to reach less integrated residents. Localised meetings, alongside general assemblies, ensured inclusive participation, while digital platforms enabled ongoing involvement, particularly for individuals with limited mobility. Accessibility and inclusivity were prioritised from the outset, with translated materials and questionnaires helping bridge language barriers, ensuring content ownership by all participants.

1.1. Structure of the document

This deliverable presents the implementation process related to the engagement strategies and methodologies developed under the SUPERSHINE project in T1.2 and T1.3 to address the socio-economic and technical challenges associated with the sustainable refurbishment of social housing. The document focuses on three pilot sites, the SUPERSHINE lighthouses of Riga (Latvia), Herning (Denmark), and Trieste (Italy). It describes a comprehensive roadmap for implementing participatory processes that align with the principles of the New European Bauhaus (NEB) - sustainability, aesthetics, and inclusivity - while tackling key issues such as energy efficiency, social cohesion, and resident empowerment.

The document begins with an **overview of the socio-economic context of the lighthouses** (Section 2), drawing on previous analyses (D1.1 and D1.2) and contextual studies. This section highlights the demographic, economic, and infrastructural profiles of each site, framing the challenges faced by their respective communities. Riga, for example, grapples with ageing Soviet-era buildings, limited energy efficiency, and social disparities. Herning's focus lies in leveraging Denmark's tenant democracy to implement equitable renovations, while Trieste tackles obsolescent housing stock through an ambitious demolition and reconstruction plan based on community-identified needs.

The **participatory pathways** (Section 3) detail the tailored approaches used to engage residents in co-creation and decision-making processes. Riga utilises innovative digital platforms like Tandeems for co-design and feedback, Herning builds on tenant democracy to foster co-decision processes, and Trieste employs targeted workshops and community mapping to ensure inclusive co-creation. These pathways aim at empowering residents as active contributors to the transformation of their living environments.

Section 4 expands on these efforts, outlining the practical implementation of the **social engagement activities**, with a qualitative approach, and the strategies for their monitoring, through a quantitative analysis carried out on the basis of the SUPERSHINE Social Engagement KPIs measurement. **Subsection 4.1, Engagement Activities and Monitoring**, provides detailed timelines, workshops, and participatory events conducted at each lighthouse level. For example, Riga integrates physical workshops and digital platforms, while Herning incorporates community-based labs and collaborative planning for energy technologies.

Subsection 4.2, Social Acceptance Analysis and Monitoring, focuses on measuring residents' initial perceptions of renovating interventions using the tailored questionnaires developed by ICONS, created to monitor the SUPERSHINE Social Acceptance KPIs. This section links the technical and social dimensions of the project, ensuring that renovations align with community needs and gain widespread acceptance. The baseline datum is analysed in this document, while the endline datum, and the possible variation consequent to the active participation of the communities in envisioning the renovation of their districts, will be analysed in the second part of this deliverable, meaning **D1.4 – Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 2**.

This document also contains a brief mentioning of **replicability inputs** (Section 5), distilling lessons learned from the lighthouses into a framework for adapting these strategies to other European contexts, especially those of the four SUPERSHINE fellow cities, Belgrade (Serbia), Zaragoza (Spain), Setúbal (Portugal), and Istanbul (Turkey). This section, that will be better elaborated in D1.4, will identify best practices, such as integrating innovative financing models, community-led initiatives, and participatory governance mechanisms.

Finally, the **key takeaways aspects** and the **conclusions** (Section 6 and 7) synthesise the outcomes, emphasising the project's dual goals of improving energy efficiency and enhancing social cohesion through resident engagement.

2. Overview of the lighthouses socio-economic context

The information contained in this section is an ensemble of the specific analyses conducted in the SUPERSHINE deliverables **D1.1 – Landscape of sites socio-economic context**, and **D1.2 – Engagement Strategy and Social Acceptance KPIs**, with the framework context mainly provided by the essay by Dr. Alice Pittini from Housing Europe **'The nuts and bolts of European social housing systems'**¹. Cultural barriers to social engagement are presented, in order to better understand how they have been addressed by the SUPERSHINE “acceptance through engagement” model implementation.

2.1. Riga - Latvia

Map of the Āgenskalna Priedes district

In the heart of Riga, within the Āgenskalns neighbourhood, lies the **Āgenskalna Priedes** residential district—a symbol of a bygone era and a beacon of future potential. This complex plays a significant role in Latvia’s urban history, featuring twenty-four multi-apartment residential buildings constructed between 1959 and 1961, marking the country’s first large-scale residential housing district. In 2020, a modern residential building was added to the area, bringing the total to twenty-five structures and providing over 1,100 apartments to approximately 2,700 residents. Managed by the municipal housing company **Rīgas Namu Pārvaldnieks (RNP)**, the district offers affordable housing as part of a broader urban renewal strategy.

Overview of the district

The population of Āgenskalna Priedes reflects a rich and diverse ethnic mix, constituting a diverse and resilient community, including Latvians, Russians, Ukrainians, Belarusians, Poles, Jews, and Lithuanians. The average

resident age, slightly over 45 years, is marginally higher than the city average. Although many

residents fall within lower income brackets, the municipality provides financial support to help cover housing costs, ensuring access to essential services. Despite an unemployment rate of just 2% -

¹ www.housingeurope.eu/resource-105/the-housing-europe-review-2012

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lower than Riga's city-wide average of 4.3% - residents have an average annual income of around euros15,600, higher than the city's average. Nevertheless, many families struggle to keep their homes adequately warm in winter and cool in summer, a challenge exacerbated by outdated buildings and the lack of individual temperature control.

Financial difficulties remain a significant concern for the district. Around 5% of residents are behind on their energy bills, with the elderly and low-income households being the most affected. These groups often overlap, particularly in historically disadvantaged areas. Although national and EU grants are available to all residents, those at risk of energy poverty are less likely to take advantage of these funds. This hesitation arises from a combination of limited awareness and scepticism about the effectiveness of energy efficiency measures.

The district's centralised heating system maintains a minimum indoor temperature of 16°C during winter, ensuring protection from extreme cold. However, it leaves residents with limited control over their heating preferences, reducing opportunities for cost-saving adjustments. Cooling needs in Latvia are minimal, with most residents relying on natural ventilation instead of mechanical cooling systems. Nonetheless, poorly insulated buildings often develop cold spots, leading to health issues, while high energy bills contribute to stress among low-income residents.

Poor insulation is the primary factor exacerbating energy poverty, particularly in the Hruschovka buildings, constructed when heat was an industrial byproduct. These buildings, designed with minimal regard for insulation, are highly inefficient and costly to heat.

In terms of cultural barriers to engagement, the legacy of Soviet-era governance presents a significant hurdle: back then, property maintenance was managed by state agencies, fostering a culture of limited self-responsibility for building upkeep. This attitude persists, hindering participation in energy efficiency projects, as many residents remain wary of government-led initiatives, with older generations particularly distrustful of authorities. There is also scepticism toward Riga's municipal housing management company, which is often perceived as ineffective or self-serving.

Concerns about financial risks further complicate this matter as well: while residents, as apartment owners, do not fear rent increases, they question whether energy savings will justify the costs of renovations. This scepticism is partly informed by past experiences with poorly executed renovations, which led to problems such as mould growth post-insulation. Misunderstandings about building physics, such as doubts about the necessity of insulating thick brick walls, further fuel resistance.

Furthermore, residents' beliefs about energy efficiency initiatives are shaped by both cultural and practical considerations: although all apartment owners have a say in decision-making, some perceive renovations as being imposed without sufficient consultation. This perception, though inaccurate, can lead to resistance. While temporary relocation is not required during renovations, many residents view the process as disruptive to their daily routines.

Perceptions are also divided: approximately half of the residents see energy-efficient renovations as an enhancement to their quality of life, while the other half regard them as unnecessary disruptions. Concerns about costs and fears of mould formation contribute to this split. Aesthetic considerations also play a role, as residents value the appearance of their buildings and expect proposed changes to respect these preferences.

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In terms of values, immediate financial benefits and comfort take precedence over long-term environmental goals. Environmental sustainability is often understood in the context of shared outdoor spaces rather than energy savings. This focus on communal well-being reflects cultural priorities but does not consistently translate into support for private building upgrades.

Decades of centralised control have influenced norms of communal living in Āgenskalna Priedes. For example, year-round window ventilation habits conflict with modern energy-saving systems, such as recuperative ventilation, which are rarely adopted due to high costs. Civic participation in Latvia remains generally low, with mixed reactions to government-led initiatives. While younger residents show interest when funding opportunities are available, older generations remain more sceptical.

Expectations for energy efficiency programmes centre on comfort, cost savings, and the long-term safety of buildings. Renovation payback periods, often exceeding 20 years, deter enthusiasm. Subsidy schemes that reduce this to around 20 years are more acceptable. Additionally, widespread distrust means some residents expect to be closely involved in monitoring renovation work to ensure proper implementation.

Language and cultural diversity present challenges to inclusivity in Āgenskalna Priedes. While many residents are Latvian speakers, Russian-speaking residents often struggle to access information, particularly as Russian is phased out as a public communication language. Elderly residents also face barriers due to limited digital skills, reducing their ability to participate in discussions and decision-making processes.

Efforts to improve accessibility include multilingual community meetings and workshops, which have been effective when well-promoted. The Riga Energy Agency's One-Stop-Shop (OSS) has been instrumental in addressing these gaps, offering personalised support and attending community meetings to provide guidance. However, greater use of alternative communication formats, such as visual guides and multilingual materials, is needed to ensure full engagement from all residents.

All above considered, the neighbourhood presents itself as a living ecosystem desiring transformation. Its periphery is lined with schools, medical offices, shops, green spaces, recreational centres, and cultural venues, complemented by an efficient public transport network. Recent upgrades have enhanced public infrastructure, including modern lighting systems, underground waste sorting facilities, and new playgrounds for children. All buildings are connected to centralised heating and hot water systems, powered by cogeneration thermal energy. Yet, the mix of public and private property ownership presents a challenge for the Municipality, delaying energy efficiency projects by up to two years in some cases. Despite these hurdles, the district has been chosen as a pilot area under the city's **Sustainable Development Programme 2021–2027**.

Plans for improving the district include upgrades to building envelopes, such as insulating external walls, roofs, attic floors, and cellar ceilings, alongside installing PVC windows and replacing external doors for greater energy efficiency. A comprehensive renovation of the heating system is also proposed, enabling individual temperature regulation to improve comfort and efficiency. Additionally, ventilation systems will be upgraded to ensure optimal air quality. In terms of renewable energy, rooftop photovoltaic panels are planned for communal energy use, with the potential for individual use in the future, further reducing energy costs and environmental impact.

The condition of some apartments and households highlights the socio-economic struggles faced by residents: damp walls, deteriorating floors, and leaking roofs are common issues, the result of

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decades without significant renovations. Moreover, the current energy crisis has significantly increased refurbishment costs, with prices rising from 127 to 400 euros per square metre. Despite these challenges, initiatives such as the **Riga Energy Efficiency Fund** and EU funding are unlocking new opportunities to accelerate renovations. A municipal ESCO (Energy Service Company) service is already managing 23 buildings in the district, providing services such as cleaning, waste management, and emergency repairs.

With the SUPERSHINE project, residents are exploring the creation of a local NGO, while the Municipality continues to support small community-led projects aimed at enhancing public spaces. Renovation plans not only target energy efficiency but also seek to enhance the aesthetic appeal and practical functionality of buildings, aligning with the EU's emphasis on the "Beauty" pillar of the New European Bauhaus, intended not only in terms of visual prominence (significant also for the social image from the outside glance towards the neighbourhood), but also of matching the community's needs.

As the following paragraphs will show, the SUPERSHINE project has showed how the Āgenskalna Priedes district is more than just a historic site: it is a laboratory for sustainable living, where technical and social challenges meet opportunities for regeneration and innovation.

A best practice to inspire the community-led renovation for Āgenskalna Priedes

The Kristapa 18 Building, before and after the renovation process.

In 2023, the first renovated building in the neighbourhood, referred to as the "Kristapa 18 building" from the street it is located in, was given new life, marking the beginning of a significant transformation process.

The extensive refurbishment, which required an investment of €860,000, resulted in a complete overhaul of the structure, making the building modern and functional. To finance the project, a 17-year loan was secured, with monthly payments ranging from €48 to €72 per flat, depending on the size.

This change not only improved the building but also fostered a renewed sense of community in the neighbourhood, inspiring the SUPERSHINE co-creation process towards a community-led renovation of the entire district.

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The Kristapa 18 heat energy reduction after renovation

The two charts above compare the heat energy consumption (including DHW) of the Riga demo buildings in 2021 and 2023. For the Kristapa 18 building, consumption has significantly decreased following the renovation process completed in 2023, dropping from a high level, represented by the red column in the first chart, to a considerably lower value in the second chart, highlighted by the green column. This change reflects a significant improvement in energy efficiency due to the interventions carried out. The Environmental Product Certifications of the building, before and after the renovation, are displayed in **Annex 1**.

2.2. Herning – Denmark

In the heart of **Herning Municipality**, within Denmark’s Midtjylland Region, lies the **FaellesBo district**, a residential area notable for its diversity and the challenges associated with energy efficiency. This neighbourhood is not just a place to live but also a testing ground for innovative solutions aimed at enhancing housing sustainability and quality of life supported by a peculiar form of “**tenant democracy**” that will be explored in the following paragraph, in terms of their role in the SUPERSHINE engagement path.

A FaellesBo district building facade

The FaellesBo district is home to a population of approximately 51,000 people spread across 1,324 square kilometres, yielding a relatively low density of 39 inhabitants per square kilometre. Despite the sprawling nature of the district, its residents enjoy a wealth of public services, including access to schools, medical facilities, shopping centres, public transport, green spaces, cycling paths, and cultural hubs. Yet, beneath this seemingly idyllic setting, socio-economic challenges persist.

The community comprises a diverse demographic mix. The majority of residents, approximately 74%, are under 60 years old, and a significant proportion, around 70%, are in employment. However, educational attainment is a concern, with half of the

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population lacking formal qualifications. Economic disparities are evident, as annual incomes range from €25,000 for single-person households reliant on social welfare to €80,000 for working couples. This economic stratification is compounded by a notable cultural diversity; while 80% of the residents are of Danish origin, the remaining 20% are immigrants. The social structure reveals further complexity, with 68% of households consisting of individuals living alone, 12% of whom are single parents. These statistics underscore the critical need for targeted social policies and structural improvements to foster greater community well-being and inclusivity.

Social engagement in Fællesbo is generally supported by well-established community structures, including resident boards and activity committees, which actively promote communication and participation among tenants. Informal activities, such as "Bingo" nights, have proven effective in fostering connections and encouraging resident involvement. However, significant cultural and social barriers persist.

The residents coming from ethnic minority groups often encounter language barriers that limit their ability to access information and fully participate in community initiatives. Furthermore, cultural differences in expectations and communication styles can hinder their engagement with energy efficiency programmes. They also reported their struggle to maintain adequate warmth during winter, in a more significant way than Danish residents, intensifying energy poverty and creating disparities in comfort levels.

Cultural challenges also arise in decision-making and participation. Civic engagement is predominantly led by older residents who are more accustomed to traditional processes and routines. This generational divide often discourages younger residents from participating, as they feel their perspectives are undervalued or ignored. Additionally, resistance to change among older tenants, who are less inclined to adopt new technologies or cope with disruptions caused by renovations, presents a notable obstacle to social engagement. Temporary relocations during the renovation process further compound these challenges, particularly for vulnerable groups who may feel displaced and unsettled.

Map of the district

The district's infrastructure reflects its age and evolving demands. The residential buildings, constructed between 1954 and 1965, comprise over 690 flats distributed across four main blocks. Despite renovations carried out in 1984 and 1996, many of these buildings fall short of meeting contemporary energy efficiency standards. At present, they feature central heating systems and LED lighting but lack renewable energy sources, highlighting the need for significant upgrades. The most urgent interventions include enhanced insulation, comprehensive building envelope improvements, and the modernisation of energy systems to reduce heat loss and improve overall efficiency.

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The SUPERSHINE project has been conceived to contribute to the transformative initiative that the district is carrying out to address these pressing issues, by supporting its participatory path. The FaellesBo district is realising ambitious renovations and innovations across several domains: building improvements are at the core of the plan, with a focus on replacing roofs, insulating external walls and attics, upgrading windows and doors with energy-efficient alternatives, and modernising interiors to enhance both comfort and functionality. These interior renovations include the addition of heated floors, improved soundproofing, and aesthetic upgrades such as new flooring and electrical installations. In tandem with these structural improvements, the project seeks to integrate renewable energy technologies. Rooftop solar panels will be installed to generate renewable electricity, while charging stations for electric vehicles will be established, supporting the shift towards sustainable mobility. Advanced energy management solutions, such as the implementation of Neogrid technology, will further optimise energy consumption and ensure a consistently comfortable indoor climate for residents.

The project's economic and social dimensions are equally significant. Recognising the financial constraints faced by many in the community, local Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) and the FaellesBo social housing organisation are collaborating to develop a crowdfunding scheme to fund the planned renovations. This participatory approach, combined with close collaboration between the municipality, local experts, and tenants, aims to ensure that the community remains actively involved in the transformation process. Ultimately, the SUPERSHINE project aspires to create a sustainable and inclusive living environment that reduces energy costs while improving the quality of life for FaellesBo's residents. Current data already point to promising trends, with a low proportion of households struggling to keep their homes warm in winter or cool in summer, and minimal occurrences of structural issues like damp walls or leaking roofs. The project's planned interventions aim to build upon this foundation, turning the district into a model of sustainability that reflects Denmark's broader commitment to environmental stewardship and social equity.

However, to expand this transversal renovation, the SUPERSHINE project is involving the district's community in developing co-decision paths relating to four areas of intervention planned for their living ecosystem: energy management technologies; urban reforestation; community-based labs for recycling of building materials; and photovoltaic systems instalment. The aim is to highlight the profound human impact of community-led renovations, creating a reliable narrative about the way sustainability can transform both the physical spaces people inhabit and the communities that make them their home.

The Danish 'tenant democracy'

The Danish non-profit housing system (*almene boliger*) is highly regarded across Europe for its strong focus on participatory democracy and the significant influence it grants residents in decision-making. This sector accounts for 20% of Denmark's total housing stock and accommodates over one-sixth of the population². Its democratic framework has roots in the workers' cooperative movement, as early housing organisations were worker-led initiatives aimed at providing affordable and healthy housing for the working class.

² Danmarks Statistik (2019). BOL101: Boliger efter område, beboertype, anvendelse, udlejningsforhold, ejerforhold or opførelsesår. *Danmarks Statistik*. Retrieved from <https://www.statistikbanken.dk/BOL101>

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The rapid urbanization of the late 19th century led to housing shortages and poor living conditions, particularly in working-class areas³. In response, independent housing organizations emerged, anticipating the establishment of Denmark’s welfare system. These organizations were founded on principles of solidarity, aiming to counteract the inequalities caused by market-driven housing policies. From the outset, collective ownership and democratic participation have been central to their structure.

Over time, non-profit housing became a cornerstone of Denmark’s public welfare strategy, particularly after World War II. The period from 1945 to 1990 marked the sector’s peak, driven by welfare state expansion and a national commitment to ensuring accessible, high-quality housing for all citizens. Today, the non-profit housing model remains the channel for providing social housing, addressing the needs of those excluded from market-based housing solutions. A regulatory framework governs the collaboration between municipalities and private non-profit housing organizations, which operate as independent entities with public responsibilities. Municipalities can allocate up to 25% of non-profit housing units, even though the latter are not municipally owned.

Tenant democracy (source: KAB Memo)

The governance structure of Danish non-profit housing organizations follows a self-organized democratic model⁴, outlined in the figure below. Tenants actively participate in decisions affecting their estates, electing representatives to manage estate-level boards, which also include professional managers. These tenant representatives form a wider assembly that collaborates with the organization’s professional board to make decisions at the organizational level. Financially, the system relies on tenant rents, which first repay the costs of the building of new housing estates. Once construction costs are covered, rents are reinvested in renovations, infrastructure, new projects, and social

initiatives. A portion of the accumulated funds is shared across the sector, maintaining high-quality standards in all housing estates.

Additionally, each non-profit housing organization works closely with two national yet privately operated entities: the National Building Foundation (*Landsbyggefonden*) and the Danish Building Defects Fund (*Byggeskadefonden*). These organizations are non-profit and independent of the government. They manage surplus rental income to address financial risks and share benefits across the entire non-profit housing sector.

³ Hansen, A. V., Langergaard, L. L. (2017). Democracy and non-profit housing. The tensions of residents’ involvement in the Danish non-profit sector. *Housing Studies*, 32(8), 1085-1104

⁴ Noring, L., Struthers, D., & Grydehøj, A. (2022). Governing and financing affordable housing at the intersection of the market and the state: Denmark’s private non-profit housing system. *Urban Research & Practice*, 15(2), 258-274.

2.3. Trieste - Italy

The Boito district from above

live in conditions that have been significantly affected by the buildings' age and lack of maintenance over the years. Functional obsolescence and technological shortcomings are now glaring, and the demolition and reconstruction project is not only necessary but urgent, to address these challenges.

Currently, about 49% of the families in the district are made up of single individuals, and 31% consist of couples, with an average of 2.5 inhabitants per apartment. However, after the reconstruction, it is expected that the number of inhabitants per unit will increase to 3.5. The current buildings, which lack a building passport or environmental declaration certificate, do not have central heating, hot water systems, individual ventilation, or LED lighting, and are not equipped with renewable energy sources. The reconstruction project aims to address these deficiencies by implementing the latest energy-efficient technologies. Each building, once completed, will achieve an energy performance rating of A2, a clear indication of the significant improvement in sustainability.

Map of the Boito district with intervention area and neighbouring areas

60% of households in Italy cannot adequately heat their homes in winter or cool them in summer, a statistic that is also evident in the Boito district.

The SUPERSHINE district in Boito is located in the heart of the city of Trieste, and consists of eight buildings, each showing the wear and tear of time. Built in 1951, these four-storey buildings contain 128 apartments, with 16 units per building. The total surface area of the buildings is 4,417 square metres, and the annual energy

consumption is 131 kWh/m², a figure that reflects the increasing need for extensive renovation. Today, the residents

The total cost for demolishing and rebuilding the eight buildings is estimated at 16.5 million euros, with payments spread over the next four years in equal instalments. Once the construction is completed, the buildings will not be sold privately but will remain under public ownership, allocated to low-income families who will continue to benefit from subsidised rents. Currently, the residents spend an average of 6,400 euros per year on energy consumption, which accounts for 40% of their annual salary. This situation reflects the financial strain

confronted by many Italian families: according to EUROSTAT statistics,

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Anyway, the district is well-served in terms of amenities, with schools, medical clinics, shops, public transport, green areas, and recreational centres all within easy reach. Furthermore, the Municipality of Trieste is planning the development of new infrastructures, including bicycle paths and centres for the elderly, to meet the growing needs of the local population. However, space for further development is limited, with available land mainly designated for the municipal urban plan or for ATER projects. At present, the district lacks a district heating system, energy production facilities, or renewable energy systems. Therefore, the renovation plan includes the integration of advanced energy systems to make the district more sustainable and less reliant on traditional energy sources.

Anyway, cultural challenges in Boito have a significant impact on acceptance of the intended renovation process. A substantial proportion of residents, 59% of whom earn less than €10,000 per year, often exhibit a deep mistrust of authorities, viewing energy renovation initiatives as externally imposed measures that disregard their preferences and disrupt their daily lives. This mistrust is exacerbated by scepticism regarding the benefits of energy efficiency programmes, with many fearing higher costs and inadequate returns on investment. These perceptions are rooted in a historical lack of transparency in public housing projects, creating significant obstacles to engagement and participation.

The demographic profile of future Boito residents, predominantly from economically disadvantaged groups, highlights the necessity of tailored engagement strategies. For these households, immediate comfort and family well-being are often prioritised over long-term sustainability, reflecting cultural values that favour short-term needs over broader environmental objectives. Furthermore, the lack of existing renewable energy systems, such as central district heating, limits residents' familiarity with energy-efficient practices, making them more hesitant to embrace new technologies.

All above considered, the renovation project would like to extend beyond the mere reconstruction of the buildings and aims at improving the entire infrastructure of the district, opening the social housing complex to the neighbouring communities, putting an end to an isolation dictated not only by architectural barriers but also by social ones. Significant upgrades to public utility networks are planned, along with improvements to the road system, the creation of additional parking spaces, and the enhancement of green spaces. The new buildings will be designed according to the highest standards, with particular attention to the needs of the population, including a large number of elderly residents. Technical measures will include the replacement of building envelope components, the installation of energy-efficient systems, and the implementation of renewable energy systems, such as rooftop photovoltaic panels and community wind power. Additionally, heat recovery systems for wastewater and ventilation will be integrated to further improve energy efficiency and reduce costs.

The transformation of the Boito district is not just a construction project but aspires to create an energy community that promotes the reduction of energy poverty and encourages the adoption of sustainable solutions. This renovation, funded by regional and state funds, aims at significantly improving the living conditions of the residents, fostering sustainability and reducing the risk of poverty and social exclusion. In this context, the redevelopment is not only a response to housing needs but also an opportunity to build a fairer and more sustainable future for all the inhabitants of Boito, that, thanks to SUPERSHINE-led co-creation pathways, are actively contributing to shape this future, reinforcing their sense of belonging as a community and of ownership regarding their living ecosystem.

The Micro-areas Programme of Trieste

In 1998, the Municipality of Trieste launched the “Habitat-Microareas” Programme, targeting neighbourhoods characterised by a significant presence of public housing estates. This initiative sought to promote well-being and foster social cohesion within these communities.

The Programme emerged as a collaborative effort involving public entities such as ATER of Trieste, the Municipality of Trieste, and the Giuliano Isontina University Health Agency, alongside various associations, social cooperatives, and volunteer organisations. Together, these partners implemented a series of coordinated and targeted actions spanning healthcare, education, housing, employment, and local democracy—reflecting guidelines from the World Health Organization and European institutions like the Lisbon European Council (March 2000) and the European Commission’s “Agenda for Social Policy” (February 2005). Initially designed exclusively for tenants living in ATER-managed properties, the initiative was later expanded to encompass families residing in neighbouring areas, the so-called “microareas.”

The Habitat-Microareas Programme pursues several overarching goals:

- Protecting health and preventing social distress.
- Fostering community development by encouraging active participation, socialisation, and the formation of resident associations to promote communication, solidarity, and mutual assistance.
- Enhancing quality of life and living conditions.
- Providing care and preventive support for vulnerable individuals.

Currently, Trieste boasts 14 Habitat-Microareas centres, each equipped with a *Social Concierge* desk. These centres provide a wide range of services aligned with the activities of the promoting entities. They act as points of contact for healthcare, social assistance, and housing-related enquiries, referrals, and requests.

Open to the wider community, these centres serve as pivotal hubs in their respective areas. They host events and socio-recreational activities tailored to residents, including shared meals and community libraries, with a particular focus on supporting the most vulnerable. Such initiatives aim at strengthening neighbourhood ties and cultivate a sense of solidarity and shared identity.

Additionally, in collaboration with the Third Sector, the programme addresses individual needs through direct support, such as assisting with shopping, medication collection, after-school tutoring, and providing companionship for elderly residents. Occasionally, the programme extends its reach by organising community events and activities in local districts, further animating the social fabric of the city.

3. Overview of the Lighthouses Participatory Paths

It is important to highlight how each lighthouse has developed its own distinct identity in community engagement, shaped by their respective approaches to co-creation. Each lighthouse orients itself towards different facets of this process – whether through co-creation, co-decision, or co-development –, as they collaboratively shape the future vision of the district.

In the **Boito district**, co-creation sessions were initiated with the support of facilitators to reimagine building appearances, green areas, and public spaces. These efforts included bespoke meetings designed for specific groups, ensuring that every voice could contribute to shaping the district's transformation.

In the **Faellesbo district**, the focus has been on fostering co-decision processes in collaboration with tenant boards. Together, they are addressing four key areas of intervention: implementing energy management technologies, promoting urban reforestation, encouraging the recycling of building materials, and expanding the use of photovoltaic systems. This participatory approach ensures that tenants play an active role in defining the district's sustainable future.

Meanwhile, the **Āgenskalna Priedes district** has embarked on an ambitious process of co-designing its renewal. This has been achieved through a combination of digital tools, such as Tandeems, and hands-on physical workshops, enabling a dynamic and inclusive dialogue between residents and stakeholders.

Through these tailored approaches, each lighthouse has embraced its own path, reflecting the power of collaboration and community-driven innovation in shaping vibrant and sustainable neighbourhoods. The paragraphs below will provide a more detailed overview of each Lighthouse participatory path.

All the engagement roadmaps, developed by ICONS's Social Innovation Team with the support of the Lighthouse Managers, are detailed in **D1.2 – Engagement Strategy and Social Acceptance KPIs**.

3.1. Riga – Latvia

The Riga Lighthouse Engagement Roadmap represented a structured and participatory process aimed at involving residents and local stakeholders in the design, planning, and implementation of interventions to enhance the energy efficiency of multi-apartment buildings. The primary goal was to develop a sustainable model for financing renovations, raise community awareness of the benefits of such initiatives, and provide financial tools to make the costs more affordable.

For logistics reasons and availabilities from technical experts to be involved in the activities, REA, the lighthouse manager, had to organise the launch of the activities (phase 1) and the first event of the second phase when the roadmap was not yet completed (as it was intended for December 2023,

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and, back then, was still in early drafting phase). Nevertheless, the intended initial activities had already been discussed among REA and ICONS, and agreed as a strategic starting point for the Āgenskalna priedes engagement path, and the feedback on the approach, as well as the challenges encountered, helped ICONS in fine-tuning the final version of the roadmap during the co-creation session held in York, in November 2023, on the occasion of the first SUPERSHINE annual meeting.

The engagement roadmap primarily mentioned as targets the residents and tenants of the buildings, considering them both as beneficiaries of the interventions and as agents of change. At the same time, it planned to engage technical professionals such as architects, engineers, and designers to ensure effective collaboration in planning and executing the renovations. Below, a brief overview of the five phases included in the roadmap, the first two of them have been successfully completed by the Riga Lighthouse by October 2024.

Phase 1 - Awareness and Launch of Activities: In June 2023, the Riga lighthouse kicked off its engagement path with a neighbourhood festival aimed at establishing an initial connection with residents and initiating dialogue on the need for interventions. The goals for this phase included fostering a cohesive community, identifying residents' needs, and introducing the project to approximately 400 participants. During this phase, the baseline datum for social acceptance was collected.

Phase 2 - Planning of Interventions: Between October 2023 and 2024, the roadmap scheduled a transition into the planning phase. The first planned activity was an initial meeting in autumn 2023, during which Riga's city architect was to present a vision for the neighbourhood's development and showcase good practice examples from both local and international contexts. Subsequently, a seminar was planned for December to provide residents with training on the renovation process and available funding opportunities.

From January 2024 onwards, the project included plans to initiate individual consultations to monitor renovation progress. Another planned activity in the early months of the year involved establishing a resident advisory group to actively support the project's objectives.

By June 2024, a co-design workshop was intended to engage approximately 80 participants in defining the aesthetic features of the buildings and shared spaces, such as the colour of façades or the reorganisation of non-habitable areas like cellars. Finally, a workshop scheduled for September aimed at enabling participants to discuss and validate proposed financial tools.

Phase 3 - Implementation of Works: In 2025, the operational phase of the works will begin, accompanied by an analysis of the social perception of the interventions, through a second administration of the SUPERSHINE social acceptance monitoring questionnaire, and the consequent comparison of this endline datum with the baseline collected in Phase 1. Concurrently, progress will be documented through photographs, videos, and interviews to disseminate results and highlight the project's impact. This documentation activity will continue until the early months of 2026.

Phase 4 - Post-Intervention Analysis: In 2027, a feasibility study will be conducted to assess the potential for replicating the model in other urban contexts. This step will conclude the process, leaving behind a structured and replicable approach to promoting sustainable and inclusive renovations.

3.2. Herning – Denmark

As detailed in paragraph 2.2, in Denmark, social housing companies play a crucial role in transforming housing renovations implementation into participatory processes, combining energy efficiency with social equity, to contribute to a transversal “just transition”. A fundamental feature of these organisations is the aforementioned **tenant democracy**, meaning the active involvement in decision-making of all the tenants living in social housing compounds, where residents actively participate in validating all the energy efficient renovation plans, through the mediation of their elective boards of tenants, as well as through regular general assemblies, and are involved in every stage, from conception to completion.

The renovation vision in the Herning lighthouse revolves around an ambitious idea: transforming the way the community live by making their urban ecosystem more sustainable, energy-efficient, and respectful of biodiversity. It is structured around four main lines of action: the installation of photovoltaic systems with battery packages, optimised heat management, the reintroduction of natural elements to promote biodiversity, and the reuse of construction materials. Each activity involves the community actively collaborating to bring this shared vision to life. The SUPERSHINE project is working to contribute not only to urban renovations, but to a vision for change towards a greener, more mindful society where every stakeholder, from individual residents to the broader community, plays a fundamental role.

A roadmap was created by ICONS for each line of action, encompassing phases of awareness-raising, planning, implementation, and consolidation.

Phase 1 - Awareness phase

The initial phase was planned to focus on raising awareness and launching activities. Meetings and workshops with tenants were considered pivotal, aiming at securing proper support by the community to proceed with the works. The social acceptance questionnaire was planned to be used to gauge the initial level of acceptance and monitor changes in perception over time.

Phase 2 - Planning phase

This phase delved into the specifics of design and preparation. For photovoltaic systems, for instance, it foresaw a process of defining how tenants interact with the new energy installations, selecting financial instruments, and approving technical details, such as the installation of solar panels. Simultaneously, plans were drawn up to optimise heat management and select the departments to be included.

Phase 3 - Implementation phase

During this phase, the planned works were planned to come to fruition. For biodiversity, for example, training sessions were planned to be organised to educate residents on enhancing surrounding natural spaces. In the case of construction material reuse, capacity-building sessions were supposed to be held to raise awareness about recycling during renovations.

Phase 4 - Consolidation phase

The final phase was inserted to ensure the sustainability of the outcomes, as well as to monitor the impact of the interventions on the social perception of the community, comparing the data collected through the questionnaire in Phase 1 with those of a second administration. Training sessions was

set to help residents adopt long-term sustainable behaviours, covering areas such as energy management, biodiversity, and recycling. Additionally, a feasibility analysis was planned to be conducted to explore the replication of this model in other settings.

3.3. Trieste – Italy

The Trieste lighthouse roadmap outlines a path of social and urban transformation aiming at promoting energy savings, community cohesion, and an improved quality of life. The narrative unfolds through several phases.

Phase 1: Awareness and Engagement

From April to July 2024, social events were planned to be held to inform the community about the project, explaining the overall plan and initiating co-design activities. This engagement was set to enable residents, local authorities, schools, and other stakeholders to collaborate actively.

Phase 2: Design Phase: Collaborative Creation of Spaces

Between July and December 2024, participatory design was planned to take central stage. Through workshops and questionnaires, residents envision the district's future, defining aesthetic aspects, green spaces, and pedestrian and cycling paths. Younger targets were planned to be included to contribute creative ideas for parks, while artists and schools explore the connection between community and urban space. Plans were also made for new services, such as markets, essential shops, and leisure initiatives.

Phase 3: Renovation Phase: Training and Updates

In 2025, renovation works will begin. Future tenants participate in training programmes to become familiar with the refurbished spaces and energy-efficient technologies. A dedicated website provides regular updates on the project's progress, ensuring transparency and ongoing engagement.

Phase 4: Transition Phase: Living the Change

In 2026, the community celebrates the completion of the works with neighbourhood events. Sociologists and psychologists lead workshops to foster civil cohabitation, prevent conflicts, and promote a sense of belonging. A new neighbourhood hub is inaugurated, serving as the focal point for social activities and services.

Phase 5: Final Phase: Monitoring and Continuity

Following the interventions, the results are assessed through questionnaires to evaluate social acceptance of the transformations. A community advisory group proactively addresses any issues, ensuring that the district remains a model of sustainability and integration.

This roadmap is not merely an operational plan but a narrative that connects people, spaces, and ideas, steering towards a more inclusive and sustainable future.

4. Social Engagement Activities

4.1. Engagement Activities and Monitoring

4.1.1. Riga – Latvia

The Riga Lighthouse is adopting a holistic approach that not only addresses the buildings but also focuses on the sustainability of the neighbourhood's living ecosystem. It emphasises collective efforts in mitigating and adapting to climate change, promoting sustainable mobility, green infrastructure, and nature-based solutions. Additionally, it integrates renewable energy sources (RES) and harnesses the benefits of digital technologies, all contributing to the overall enhancement of the quality of life, well-being, and health of the district's residents.

Starting from 2023 and concluding in October 2024, the Āgenskalna priedes community has successfully completed the first two phases of their tailored engagement roadmap, meaning the phase of “Awareness and launch of the activities” and the phase of “Design of renovation works”, implementing a process of co-designing the district overall renewal, layered on three different levels of intervention:

- the building level,
- the common areas and inyards level, and, finally,
- the entire district intended as a whole.

The co-design has been carried out through a specific double-faceted approach, using both digital support tools for citizen engagement as well as other types of discussion spaces to keep the district community always in touch, i.e. the digital platform “Tandeems⁵”. Tandeems is an original Latvian platform, developed by REA and the NGO Tandeems, created for conducting online design competitions and workshops, and that includes a library of tools to fit a variety of competition formats, educational tasks and user surveys. The goal was to cultivate a transparent, digital and competitive co-design process that can meaningfully engage local community, various user groups, general public and experts, through activities going from architectural intervention modelling, to focus groups and online workshops, and physical workshops with the district community (nine workshops up to October 2024). This layered approach allowed the Riga lighthouse to widen its audience beyond the selected community, exchanging ideas and validating the most technical proposals of professionals in the sector.

During the physical workshops with the community stakeholders, the participants co-designed the development vision and strategy for the energy retrofits and revitalisation of the whole housing block. Up to October 2024, the lighthouse of Riga carried out a community-led co-designing of the block, making customised architectural visualisations of future renovation and growth of the district, also developing plans to use the participatory budget from the City of Riga to renovate inn-yards and communal green areas, in order to directly assign the management on to the community, therefore creating new jobs for self-maintenance.

⁵ <https://tandeems.lv/contests/agenskalna-priedes>

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It is also worth noting that all activities incorporated an element of bottom-up participation. At the conclusion of each event, residents of the Riga demonstration site proposed various topics and voted on those they would prefer to see addressed in future engagement activities.

Furthermore, in Riga, the stakeholders showed a significant interest to be further involved in the SUPERSHINE process leading to the customisation of their lighthouse business models, and were (and will keep being) regularly updated by REA about their SUPERSHINE meetings with the consortium partners involved in the activity (UoY, CIRCE, AYMING, TENDER). This interest was due to the difficulties previously encountered by the Riga Municipality in negotiating with the government traditional forms of top-down funding schemes (so far never tested in Latvia), leading REA to search in SUPERSHINE for the possibility of co-designing, together with the community, a business model for bottom-up funding schemes, allowing each building in the district to have its own financial scheme.

Engagement timeline for the RIGA lighthouse co-design workshops

Kick-off of the engagement activities

The kick-off event of the SUPERSHINE engagement path was held in June 2023 during the Quarter Festivity, that represented an important opportunity to introduce the SUPERSHINE project to local residents and establish the first networks of collaboration, despite the engagement strategy was yet in the process of being defined in its objectives and peculiarities.

With a participatory approach, active citizens were engaged, forming a direct link for future events. Although the event was somewhat costly, it proved to be a valuable investment for long-term collaboration with the local community. While most participants (more than one hundred in total) showed little interest in the technical aspects of the project, it became clear that presenting clear

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goals and a defined timeline is essential to maintain engagement and encourage ongoing involvement.

A shot from the kick-off in Riga

‘Community-led development’ workshop

The aim of this workshop was to establish a connection between the chief architect of Riga and the residents, providing an opportunity to discuss his vision for the potential development of the quarter, as well as gather input from the inhabitants on possible solutions. However, the constructive engagement with residents was hindered by the architect's presentation of the proposed solution, which was not well thought out. Despite this, valuable input was collected from the community regarding their concerns and ideas.

The workshop proved that, despite the enthusiasm and the positive attitude from the community side, clear communication is crucial at all times from the practitioners, that should be able to communicate the innovation of intended solutions in an accessible manner, especially when residents might perceive certain proposals as a threat to the peace of their daily lives.

Similar to the kick-off event, this workshop was held for logistics and experts' availabilities reasons before the SUPERSHINE engagement strategy by ICONS was completed. Therefore, REA, as pilot manager, made good use of this experience by working with ICONS in having the SUPERSHINE engagement strategy tailored to tackle this communication barrier among the technical experts and the district inhabitants.

Scenes from the 'community-led development' workshop

The SUPERSHINE Hackathon

For the seventh consecutive year, in November 2023, Riga hosted the influential international urban planning forum "MadCity 2023", thus fostering collaboration and innovation in the city's urban development. The "MadCity 2023" forum brought together urban planners, architects, municipal experts, and other interested parties with a shared goal: to co-create innovative solutions that would help transform the Āgenskalna priedes district and other micro-districts of Riga into vibrant, thriving communities.

Among the key events during the forum, the Mayor of Riga, Vilnis Ķirsis, visited the Āgenskalna priedes district to meet with residents. He engaged in meaningful conversations, answering their questions about the potential future development of the area from a municipal perspective. In addition, a hackathon was organised, where participants focused on brainstorming creative ideas for the quarter's development.

The event was dedicated to addressing one of Riga's most pressing urban challenges: the revitalisation and re-humanisation of Soviet-era micro-districts, raising the issue of dissonant architectural heritage. In addition to recalling a recent and problematic past, the Sovietic areas face numerous issues, including ageing housing, outdated public spaces, and a lack of urban environments that promote social interaction and cooperation among residents. During the forum, new and unconventional solutions were developed, with the aim of making the Āgenskalna priedes district a more enjoyable, integrated, and sustainable place to live.

Images from the SUPERSHINE hackathon at 'MadCity 23' festival.

'Energy retrofits' workshop

The "Energy retrofits" workshop brought together the lead energy efficiency expert from REA, with a particular focus on building renovation. It was part of REA's regular One-stop-shop service, which provides consultations on building renovations. What set this session apart from business as usual was its SUPERSHINE-inspired focus on the single district of Āgenskalna priedes, which raised unique questions and considerations, resulting from direct and active involvement of the district tenants, such as exploring potential cost-saving opportunities under the framework of SUPERSHINE innovative financial tools analysis.

As with all One-stop-shop meetings, the consultants involved were expected to be well-versed in a range of topics, offering expertise across various aspects of building renovation. However, when questions arose that could not be immediately answered, it was essential that a clear pathway be provided to the consultee, ensuring they knew how to access the required information at a later

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stage. To meet this need, the SUPERSHINE toolkit will be further integrated and put at community's disposal, and this aspect was taken into consideration by the SUPERSHINE consortium in the process of shaping the project's own one-stop-shop, currently in elaboration phase.

Shots from the 'Energy retrofits' workshop

'Reinforcing the community values' workshop

Shot from the event

The purpose of the meeting was to help residents shape a vision for their urban living ecosystem, thus to be rooted in shared values. While the focus was on fostering this new way of thinking, the topic of building renovation also emerged briefly.

By the end of the meeting, a solid foundation had been laid for creating a value-driven vision for the area. The residents were introduced to a fresh perspective on how to approach the development of their community, one that might have felt different from their usual way of thinking.

However, in hindsight, the meeting may have been too broad in scope. The inclusion of building renovation discussions, while relevant, ended up distracting from the main goal. A more focused approach, that is to say centred solely on the vision for the district, might have yielded even more meaningful insights and clearer direction.

'Visioning the future' workshop

Vērtības balstīta
Āgenskalna priekšu kvartāla
attīstības vīzija – semināru cikls

2. seminārs –
Kāds izskatās mūsu nākotnes
kvartāls?

3. jūnijs plkst. 18:30
Pie skulpturparka-strūklīkas Āgenskalna ielā 24

Dosimies kvartālā kopā ar arhitektu
un pilsētplānotājiem, izvērtējot
labiekārtošanas iespējas!

Lūdzam pieieties
līdz 30. maijam:
ej.uz/seminars2AP

RĪGAS ENERĢĒTIKAS
AGENTŪRA

Pasākuma
organizācija:
Rīgas Enerģētiskā
Agentūra
+371 29 326 910 vai zinas@energetika.lv

Event poster

During this workshop, the team of architects from the NGO Tandeems was introduced to the district inhabitants, and a potential collaboration with them was outlined (that would have then resulted in the shared Tandeems platform for the Riga lighthouse co-design process).

To engage the residents, the event included a walking tour where participants took photos of the areas they least liked in the quarter, capturing them at different planning scales. The residents then proposed possible improvements for these spots, which were later shared and voted on through the Tandeems digital platform, back then in the early development phase.

This marked the launch of a digital participation process, giving the inhabitants a chance to contribute their ideas and feedback on potential solutions for the area. As an external organisation, Tandeems was able to connect with the residents in a way that the Municipality, perhaps, could

not. Their outsider status seemed to make them more approachable. However, despite this connection, the technical nature of the information initially made it difficult to capture the full attention of the attendees. Over time, though, their involvement became more engaging as the process unfolded. Finally, the decision to use the Tandeems digital platform for the SUPERSHINE participatory purpose allowed the platform to be tested with a wider audience and fine-tuned.

A shot from the 'Visioning the future' workshop

‘Development of the potential renewal (buildings and innyards)’ workshop

In this meeting, the results from the digital participatory forum held on the Tandeems platform were carefully analysed and shared with the residents. The conversation then shifted back to refining the value-based vision for the district, with further work undertaken to develop a shared sense of direction.

To keep the momentum going, the residents were given some "homework", meaning tasks to complete on the digital platform, encouraging them to continue their involvement and contribute more ideas.

Throughout the session, it became clear that building trust with the inhabitants was a crucial element in the process. This required a diverse approach, one that acknowledged the individual needs and concerns of the residents. Ultimately, it was the people skills of the team that proved most important in fostering a collaborative and open atmosphere.

Event poster

Regular workshops for ‘Vision and Next Steps’

19. augusts, plkst. 18.30

Āgenskalna priedes, pie skateparka–strūklakas

Semināru cikla "Vērtībās balstīta Āgenskala priekšu attīstības vizija" noslēguma pasākums

PROGRAMMA:

- 18.30 - 19.10 **Āgenskalna priekšu iedzīvotāju veidotās vizijas prezentācija**
Arhitekts Kārlis Jaurimāns un Zane Ruģēna no Rīgas enerģētikas aģentūras
- 19.10 - 20.00 **Darba grupas. Aicinām iedzīvotājus iesaistīties vienā no interesējošām grupām!**
- 1) Vai biedrības dibināšana mums palīdzēs atrisināt bedres asfaltā?
Kā biedrība var risināt sasāpējušus apsaimniekošanas jautājumus? Vai iespējams mainīt apsaimniekotāju? Kādas perspektīvas vēl iespējamas, dibinot biedrību?
Moderē Nika Kotoviča un Volters Liberts Muzikants, Rīgas enerģētikas aģentūra
- 2) No vārdiem pie darbiem!
Grupa aktīvajiem iedzīvotājiem, kuri gatavi rīkot iedzīvotāju talku Āgenskalna priekšu kvartālā šī gada septembrī! SUPERSHINE projekts var palīdzēt iedzīvotājiem īstenot talkas ideju, piedāvājot dažāda veida konsultatīvu atbalstu, kā arī līdzdalību koordinēšanā.
Moderē arhitekts Kārlis Jaurimāns un Zane Ruģēna no Rīgas enerģētikas aģentūras
- 3) Ēku atjaunošana. Praktiski.
Turpmākie soļi un finansējums.
Moderē Anis Leļitis, Rīgas enerģētikas aģentūra
- Darba grupu rezultātu prezentācijas. Semināra darba sesijas noslēgums.**
- No 20:00 **Meistarklase un degustācija "Apkaimes iedzīvotāju saliedēšana caur kopā gatavotu ēdienu". Āgenskalna priekšu iedzīvotāju mīļāko receptu prezentācija.**
Sēpavārs Havjers Garsija
- Apkaimes iedzīvotāju saliedēšanas meistarklase: improvizācijas teātris "Kaimiņi".**
Imersīvā zīmējumu izrāde "Kaimiņa dārza anatomija"
Neatkarīgas profesionālās teātris "Zīmējumu teātris"
- No 21:00 **Neformālā daļa, mūzika, uzskodos, sarunas.**

Starting from August 2024, a series of workshops were held, each one focused on addressing the problems previously identified and exploring potential solutions. To make the experience more engaging, a non-formal segment was also included in the agenda, allowing for a more relaxed atmosphere and fostering connections among participants.

During the sessions, clear tasks and schedules were established for the next steps: some participants were tasked with contributing to building renovation efforts, while others took part in a communal gardening project in the quarter, bringing a sense of collaboration to the process.

It became evident that connecting the residents through the shared history of the district was an effective approach, also to support them in dealing with the Soviet legacy and the dissonant architectural heritage.

This narrative not only sparked interest but also helped to build a sense of community, with a clearer sense of ownership towards their homes compared to the past. Moving forward, it emerged that, for future activities to succeed, responsibility and communication channels must be clearly defined, ensuring everyone knows their role and how to stay informed.

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'Vision and next steps' poster agenda and shots

As a result of the SUPERSHINE co-design participatory path, the Āgenskalna priedes district inhabitants produced concrete materials containing their community-shaped vision for the future radical renovation of the district. Some of those materials are presented in the pictures below.

Renders and maps of the community-shaped vision for the district

Big clean-up community event

The community participating the clean-up event

The day was dedicated to a hands-on co-working session focused on the tangible aspect of building renovation. A flower-bed feature in the quarter was cleared of debris, and the ground was levelled where needed, transforming the space with visible effort and teamwork.

This event turned out to be more than just a practical task: it became a strong communal

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experience, one that brought people together through shared work and common interests. By the end of the day, there was a clear, rewarding result that everyone could take pride in. Such short-term activities play a crucial role in uniting a community, especially when larger projects like building renovation can span years. Without these smaller, more immediate actions, it is easy for the connection between neighbours to fade, leaving the community feeling disconnected from one another in the long wait for bigger changes.

4.1.1.1. Progress monitoring in SE KPIs achievement

Table 1 below presents the Social Engagement KPIs collected by the Riga demo site for the activities described in 4.1.1. This set of KPIs evaluates the effectiveness of engagement in demo sites, addressing factors such as the ratio between target participants and actual attendees. The KPIs are the means to monitor the implementation of the engagement roadmap described in detail in D1.2, covering *Phase 1: Awareness/Launch of activities*, and *Phase 2: Design of renovations works*.

The demo case constitutes a pivotal example as all activities included some form of capacity building content. During each event, Riga city experts from the Energy Renovation OSS and other municipal departments engaged directly with residents, delivering presentations and responding to questions on topics such as energy retrofits, energy efficiency of building stock, revitalisation of adjacent public space, legal procedures, available funding and financial aid programmes to support energy renovation projects. Municipalities and external experts showcased best practices and lessons learned from past energy retrofits, different technologies of renovation of the building and its engineering systems, details on costs and benefits, and explaining legal aspects for the preparation of energy retrofit projects. Furthermore, all presentations and workshop materials were consistently shared with event participants and uploaded to the Tandeems digital participation platform. This approach enables all activities described in 4.1.1 to be recognized as capacity building activities, contributing directly to the measurement of KPI4.SE.

Regarding the timespan under observation, measurements of KPI1.SE indicate that engagement targets were reached in most of activities. Notably, the first three activities, primarily focused on engaging on the community of residents, gathered more participants than expected, signalling a good responsiveness of the residents to engagement activities. However, two activities fell short of their participation target: the *'Energy retrofits' workshop* and the *'Big clean-up' community event*. These activities differed significantly in nature and audience, targeting design experts and residents. As such, no single factor can be attributed to the lower engagement in both cases. When cross-referenced with Social Awareness indicators KPI1.SA and KPI2.SA, as reported in 4.2.2.1, the lower participation for the *'Energy retrofits' workshop* may reflect a limited level of awareness and interest among residents regarding energy production and management. It is recommended that specific attention should be given to this topic during the next activities in the demo site.

Table 1: Social Engagement Indicators for Riga demo site

KPI code and name	Stakeholder Outreach (KPI1.SE)	Stakeholders Groups (KPI2.SE)	Capacity building activities (KPI4.SE)
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KPI definition	This KPI measures the number of stakeholders engaged in the LH for each activity conducted (e.g., co-design sessions, capacity building sessions, community events) according to the target set.	This KPI assesses the participation of all stakeholders' groups that the activity aims to engage in the event. For instance, if a workshop involving tenants, students and local association has been planned, it is important to verify that all stakeholders' groups have participated.	Number of SHs reached by capacity building activities or material prepared
Unit of measurement	%	%	Number
Engagement Activity 1: Kick-off of the engagement activities – 06.06.2023	(120 participants / 100 target) = 120%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	120
Engagement Activity 2: 'Community-led development' workshop – 30.10.2023	(37 participants / 30 target) = 123%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	37
Engagement Activity 3: The SUPERSHINE Hackathon – 02.10.2023	(400 participants / 300 target) = 133%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	400
Engagement Activity 4: 'Energy retrofits' workshop – 15.01.2024	(44 participants / 50 target) = 88%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	44
Engagement Activity 5: 'Reinforcing the community values' workshop – 29.04.2024	(31 participants / 30 target) = 103%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	31
Engagement Activity 6: 'Visioning the future' workshop – 03.06.2024	(34 participants / 30 target) = 113%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	34
Engagement Activity 7: 'Development of the potential renewal (buildings and innyards)' workshop – 22.07.2024	(50 participants / 50 target) = 100%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	50
Engagement Activity 8: Regular workshops for	(70 participants / 50 target) = 140%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	70

‘Vision and Next Steps’ – 19.08.2024			
Engagement Activity 9: Big clean-up community event – 28.09.2024	(8 participants / 15 target) = 53%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	8

4.1.2. Herning – Denmark

The implementation of the SUPERSHINE project in FællesBo district aims at reducing energy poverty issues by decreasing the high cost of energy bills (especially heating costs) through the installation of Photovoltaic Systems, establishing Electric Vehicles charging stations makes it possible for the tenants to apply EV (both scooters, bikes, and cars), and rewilding green areas to increase life quality in the near surroundings. Furthermore, in addition to the district tenants, several stakeholders, such as associations for social promotions, universities, artists, start-up SMEs, local designers & architects, NGOs, local investors are being encouraged to contribute and co-design district activities, also widening the social engagement audience to the neighbouring community.

As mentioned above, under the aegis of SUPERSHINE, the Faellesbo district is developing co-decision paths with the community relating to four areas of intervention planned for the area:

- energy management technologies;
- urban reforestation;
- community-based labs for recycling of building materials; and
- photovoltaic systems instalment.

Up to the end of 2024, the Faellesbo lighthouse has completed the first phase of its roadmap, the awareness phase, and is about to complete the second, meaning the planning phase. Yet, the lighthouse is simultaneously beginning to lay the concrete foundations for some of the renovation works (e.g., the orangery as a result of the labs), partially entering phase three, dedicated to the implementation of the planned renovations, as it will be detailed below.

Concerning the smart energy management, the lighthouse manager is investigating, together with the community, whether they can use Danfoss ECL, meaning intelligent temperature controllers for district heating (DH), district cooling (DC), domestic hot water systems (DHW), and ventilation systems, in all the district housing departments. The community is directly involved in the decision-making, collaborating with project experts to assess energy savings by reviewing consumption data, energy labels, and other relevant metrics. Together, they aim at determining how these savings can be reinvested to hire an energy specialist, who will not only sustain ongoing economic benefits for the community but also provide continuous support to residents in using new technologies and managing energy more effectively.

Regarding the solar cells, a pilot system was installed in department 16 in 2023. As new tenants moved in during autumn 2024, the lighthouse manager began engaging the community in monitoring and analysing the resulting power savings. Additionally, the Board of Tenants is actively participating

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in a co-decision process concerning the financing of the intervention. The tenants expressed a preference for ESCO (Energy Service Company) financing, prompting an ongoing analysis of ESCO financing models, mandatory regulatory checks, and an energy screening in one of the largest housing departments. This process is supported externally by Sustain Technologies.

The findings from these analyses will inform decisions on establishing ESCO-financed PV systems in three additional FaellesBo departments. By the end of 2024, the lighthouse aims at reaching a conclusion on the feasibility of expanding PV installations across the entire district.

The community-based labs for recycling construction materials were established through a co-decision process in 2023 and early 2024 and are now operational with the creation of a greenhouse. Community members actively participated in laying the foundations, while students from the local vocational school contributed to the installation and assembly of the orangery. In addition, a co-designed building application for a garden shed, bonfire hut, and amphitheatre made from recycled materials was recently submitted to Herning Municipality for approval. Construction is expected to begin by early 2025. This initiative not only fosters sustainable practices but also strengthens collaboration between the community and the vocational school. Students gain hands-on experience and the opportunity to develop skills in building with recycled materials, contributing to both their education and the community's development.

Regarding urban reforestation and re-wilding, the lighthouse manager initially encountered opposition from the Board of Tenants, representing a segment of the community, composed of elderly residents who were concerned that reforestation might give the neighbourhood a less tidy appearance. This resistance gradually shifted to a more conciliatory stance following extensive dialogues and focus groups involving experts. Currently, the Faellesbo district is exploring potential collaboration with Fruehøjgaard Boligselskab to enhance local biodiversity. The community is actively evaluating their participation in projects focused on natural climate adaptation, with particular attention to biodiversity and climate accounting.

In partnership with Fruehøjgaard and supported by the SUPE team, the community is developing an inspiration catalogue to serve as a resource for all Danish housing departments. Additionally, a pilot project is underway to introduce meadow flowers and wetlands as part of climate adaptation measures in FællesBo's green common areas. This initiative is being conducted in collaboration with the "Sustainable Herning" association, other local social housing companies, and their respective boards of tenants. The project is also investigating whether daily operational savings could serve as a financing mechanism for further re-wilding initiatives, fostering long-term environmental sustainability within the community.

Engagement timeline

Questionnaire-focused meeting

Considering their role as spokesmen for the tenants of the lighthouse, the Board of Tenants was appointed with the role of collecting information concerning the sentiment of the community in terms of social acceptance of the renovations. Therefore, they organised a meeting to answer the SUPERSHINE social acceptance questionnaire with pre-aggregated data representing groups of tenants, thus providing the baseline datum for the social acceptance analysis. The responses provided by the Board of Tenants painted an overwhelmingly positive picture. The feedback highlighted high levels of social acceptance and enthusiasm for the pilot project, which focuses on energy management, photovoltaic systems, the reuse of building materials, and rewilding initiatives.

This encouraging outcome will serve as a cornerstone for the further development and implementation of the SUPERSHINE pilot activities, ensuring that these innovative solutions resonate deeply with the community's aspirations and support their long-term sustainability. The SUPERSHINE project stood out as a transformative initiative, and the tenants showed enthusiasm towards the perspective of receiving an appealing and community-centred financing models tailored to support the renovation actions in the Faellesbo district. As soon as these financing solutions are refined and presented, the questionnaire will be administered again to collect the endline datum, which will presumably be improved in terms of trusting the project's dedication to not just innovation, but also to genuine collaboration and tenant empowerment, having offered meaningful and realistic outcomes.

PV systems pilot installation validation and co-decision meeting

FB's initiative to install PV systems reflects its commitment to driving positive economic returns from its investments. With this goal in mind, FB organised informational meetings with the tenants of Department 16 to discuss the possibility of installing PV panels. The response was overwhelmingly positive, reflecting the tenants' enthusiasm for sustainable energy solutions. As a cooperative housing association, Danish social housing companies like FB rely on tenant approval to move forward with such projects. Encouraged by the supportive feedback, the tenants' board of

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Department 16 approved the PV investment, leading to the successful installation of the system in late 2023.

However, following this milestone, FB's administration received new guidance from BL, the Danish Association of Housing Cooperatives (SHCs), which posed an unexpected challenge. For Danish SHCs, the economic benefits of PV investments could not be directly realised by tenants. Instead, the gross cost of the investment would need to be absorbed as a rental expense, diminishing the appeal of PV installations for tenants. Recognising this barrier, FB began exploring innovative financing models to make future PV investments viable and attractive, with the support of SUPERSHINE financial partners. Solutions under consideration include ESCO financing and crowd-financing models, which could address the economic challenges and create pathways for more equitable and tenant-friendly investments.

The SUPERSHINE project plays a pivotal role in this effort. By leveraging its resources and collaborative framework, FB aims at identifying and testing these new financing models, setting the stage for sustainable energy solutions that benefit both the environment and the tenants. SUPERSHINE thus becomes a key enabler in turning these ambitious goals into actionable outcomes.

Stakeholders' dialogue for financing PV systems

As previously noted, the lighthouse manager needed to account for the fact that, under a business-as-usual approach, the full investment cost of PV installation would need to be incorporated into tenants' rent. This requirement has understandably led to tenants' reluctance to support the adoption of PV systems. In response to this challenge, FB is exploring innovative financing mechanisms, such as ESCO financing, to mitigate this obstacle and enhance the investment's appeal.

To initiate this process, FB has engaged with six key stakeholders to identify viable financing models for PV systems. These stakeholders include the ESCO SUSTAIN Solutions, an energy expert, the FB Handcraft Department, the FB Organisation Board, BL, other local SHCs, and the local electricity DSO company.

There has been strong interest among the stakeholders to collaborate with FB in finding effective financing solutions for PV investments. One promising avenue is ESCO financing, and SUSTAIN Solutions is currently working on a proposal for this model. For instance, an example from the SUSTAIN Technologies website, that can be seen in the picture, highlights a successful PV project for the SHC Sønderborg Andelsboligforening, offering insights into the potential for similar solutions.

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The pilot installation of PV panels in the district

Stakeholder-led administrative sessions for the construction of an orangery

The orangery worksite.

FB embarked on an innovative project to create an orangery in a shared green space, using salvaged materials from building renovations. To bring this sustainable vision to life, securing a building permit from Herning Municipality was a necessary first step. Recognising the importance of collaboration, four key stakeholders from the district community joined forces to prepare the application: Herning Municipality; Næste, a construction company specialising in material reuse and tasked with building the orangery; Titan, a demolition company involved in FB's renovation projects and the provider of the reused materials; and FB itself, coordinating the effort.

This cooperative approach proved to be a resounding success. By aligning the expertise and contributions of these stakeholders, FB not only streamlined the permit process but also laid a strong foundation for the orangery project. This positive experience has inspired FB to explore broader applications of material reuse, envisioning new constructions that incorporate salvaged materials on a larger scale.

However, FB is mindful of potential challenges. Securing building permits for reuse projects, managing additional costs tied to demolition processes, and addressing expenses related to adapting reused materials for new constructions are all hurdles that require careful consideration. To navigate these challenges, FB plans to analyse the results of the orangery project, using it as a blueprint to inform future strategies and initiatives.

With this groundwork, FB is poised to expand its material reuse efforts, demonstrating how innovative partnerships and sustainable practices can reshape the construction landscape while fostering environmental responsibility.

Regular meetings to involve students from the Herningsholm Business Academy

As part of its efforts to promote the reuse of building materials, FB embarked on an inspiring initiative: constructing an orangery in a shared green space using materials salvaged from renovation projects. To bring this vision to life, FB reached out to the local Herningsholm Business Academy, an institution dedicated to training young people in craftsmanship and technical professions. Enthusiastically embracing the collaboration, Herningsholm involved fifteen of its students in the project, working alongside twenty tenants from the community, and established a series of meeting to present the vision and the approaches for this collaboration.

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A shot from one of the meetings

The Academy students brought valuable technical expertise to the table, contributing significantly to the planning and execution of the orangery. Their knowledge of building materials and techniques proved instrumental in guiding tenants through the process, ensuring the project was both innovative and practical. While the physical construction of the orangery was completed by a professional building company, the collaboration highlighted the power of combining educational resources with community-driven initiatives.

The success of this partnership is encouraging FB to explore further collaborations with Herningsholm Business Academy. Plans are underway to extend this approach to other reuse projects and potentially even broader initiatives, such as rewilding efforts, photovoltaic systems, and more. FB is also considering partnerships with additional educational institutions, leveraging specialised expertise to amplify the impact of its sustainability projects.

This fruitful alliance demonstrates how merging education, community engagement, and sustainability can yield extraordinary results, setting a precedent for future ventures.

Building the orangery

Community-led building of a garden shed and a fireplace

As part of its commitment to sustainability, FB launched an inspiring project to build a garden shed and fireplace in a shared green space, using reclaimed materials from renovation activities as per the orangery. FB partnered again with Herningsholm Business Academy, involving the students.

The involvement of Academy pupils, with their know-how about technical issues related to buildings and construction materials, has shown up to be successful in supporting FB tenants in planning and implementing the garden shed and fire place re-using building materials from building renovation. Yet, as per the orangery, for security reasons, the final building of the garden shed and the fireplace has been carried out by a professional building company.

Anyway, the partnership with the students inside the community is becoming a shining example of how education, community involvement, and sustainability can intersect to create meaningful projects.

Involving local SMEs for a sustainable built environment

As part of the FB SUPERSHINE pilot project, FB is championing the reuse of building materials from renovation activities, a cornerstone of creating a sustainable built environment. Central to this effort is the exploration of which materials from the renovation of existing buildings can be effectively repurposed. This initiative is particularly significant given FB's ambitious plan to renovate approximately 2,000 of its 5,000 apartments, representing a substantial opportunity to rethink material use at scale.

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A critical element of this project is the collaboration with Næste, a local construction company specialising in building with reclaimed materials. Together, FB and Næste are conducting detailed inventories of salvaged wood from buildings slated for renovation. This process, undertaken by two FB staff members and two Næste specialists, involves identifying and categorising wood that holds potential for reuse, creating a specific know-how for the community with regards to sustainable construction materials.

Although the registration is still ongoing and data on the types and quantities of reusable wood is not yet available, this partnership highlights the vital role local businesses play in driving innovation in sustainable construction. By engaging Næste's expertise, FB not only accelerates its ability to identify practical solutions but also fosters a deeper understanding of sustainable materials within the local community.

Once the registration process is complete, FB will use the findings to create strategic plans for integrating salvaged wood into new construction projects. This approach not only reduces waste but also builds valuable know-how around sustainable building materials, empowering both the community and local businesses to contribute to a greener future. By prioritising local partnerships, FB demonstrates how collaboration can be a powerful tool for transforming the construction industry and embedding sustainability at the heart of the built environment.

Tenants' awareness raising meetings about rewilding

FB has embarked on an ambitious plan to rewild shared green spaces, transforming traditional lawns into vibrant, diverse ecosystems. This shift presents challenges, not least in fostering enthusiasm among tenants for a landscape characterised by wild plants, more insects, and a natural aesthetic quite different from the neatly trimmed lawns they are accustomed to. Some tenants, particularly elder residents, may feel hesitant about these changes. Similarly, FB's operational staff, responsible for maintaining these areas, must adapt to new methods of care and receive training to manage wild spaces effectively.

Room for Difference initiative representatives

Another challenge lies in financing the transition. While reduced lawn maintenance might offer operational savings, substantial upfront investments are needed to establish and manage rewilded areas. FB is exploring whether these costs can be integrated into broader building renovation budgets, where green spaces are already slated for renewal.

To kickstart the initiative, FB organised an information and discussion session involving thirty tenants and thirty board members from various departments. The dialogue was aimed at gathering perspectives and proposals on rewilding possibilities. Department 24 was chosen as the pilot area, and FB

sought funding from the Nordea Bank Fund to support the effort.

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With the involvement of local stakeholders - including the housing-social initiative *Room for Difference*, Holtebjerg Childrenhouse, FGU Nature Line (a preparatory education programme), Herningsholm Public School, Youth School UngHerning, and Holtebjerg Activity House -, FB successfully secured approximately €140,000 for the pilot project.

The next step was to engage Department 24's 270 tenants via a newsletter detailing the rewilding measures and funding opportunities. FB then hosted a meeting with ten local stakeholders, including municipal representatives, tenants, staff, environmental organisations, and local residents, to explore the project's possibilities. The group decided to begin the rewilding efforts by establishing raised plant beds. This activity brought together fifteen tenants, students from Herningsholm Business Academy, and a local entrepreneur to create the beds, marking a tangible first step in transforming the area.

FB has been encouraged by the strong interest and support from local stakeholders, the tenant board in Department 24, and the broader tenant community. The enthusiasm shown for the rewilding project is, in itself, a significant milestone, laying the groundwork for future initiatives. The results of this initial SUPERSHINE rewilding pilot will be carefully analysed to inform the planning and execution of subsequent activities. The insights gained will also help FB address barriers such as tenant hesitancy, operational challenges, and financial constraints. With the active involvement of tenants and local partners, FB is paving the way for a greener, more sustainable future while fostering community engagement and environmental stewardship.

Community-led sessions for identifying financing models for energy management technologies

FB has decided to install energy management systems with the aim of saving energy, increasing the share of renewable energy in the energy supply, and reducing energy costs for tenants. There is significant potential to achieve these benefits, thanks to the large share of cost-efficient renewable energy in the Danish energy system, which, through effective energy management, could cover a greater portion of electricity consumption. However, it is not possible to obtain attractive low-cost financing for the installation of these systems through conventional deep building renovation funding. Therefore, FB faces the challenge of identifying and testing appealing funding solutions for energy management systems.

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The Neogrid PreHeat Energy Management System functioning process explained

As part of the SUPERSHINE pilot activity, FB aimed at identifying and, if possible, testing energy management systems through a participatory path with the tenants. As a first step, FB has involved several community stakeholders, meaning its own FB Handcraft department, the organisational board, the operational staff department, and external partners Danfoss and Neogrid Technologies, suppliers of energy management systems, along with an external energy expert. The goal was to identify the most suitable systems for FB.

In collaboration with Danfoss and Neogrid Technologies, FB has selected the Danfoss ECL and Neogrid Technologies PreHeat energy management systems, deemed appropriate for application and testing within the SUPERSHINE pilot activity. Following the testing phase, these systems will form the basis for further plans to install and operate energy management systems as part of the SUPERSHINE pilot activities. A key aspect of this process will be identifying attractive financing mechanisms for energy management systems, including the potential for crowd and ESCO financing models.

Training sessions on energy management technologies

FB has identified the Danfoss ECL and Neogrid Technologies' Preheat systems as viable solutions for energy management. Recognising the importance of empowering their team, FB has embarked on a crucial journey to train both technical and administrative staff in the effective use of these systems. Three staff members from the FB Handcraft department and four from the administrative team are undergoing comprehensive training to apply the Danfoss ECL and Neogrid Preheat systems. The goal is to enable them to manage domestic water, heating, and ventilation systems efficiently, leading to significant energy savings.

This training initiative is not just a step in the SUPERSHINE pilot activity: it represents a fundamental part of FB's strategy to build a sustainable future. The importance of this training cannot be overstated, as it lays the foundation for FB to expand its use of energy management technologies. As staff become proficient in managing and maintaining these systems, FB will be able to implement and operate energy-saving technologies more effectively, reducing reliance on external support and fostering a long-term, self-sufficient approach to energy management. By equipping their staff with the knowledge and skills to operate these advanced energy management systems, FB aims at creating a self-sustaining model for system maintenance and operation, to be extended to the tenants' themselves later on, paving the road to the creation of new expertise and jobs.

Collaborative analysis on energy savings patterns and certificates

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As part of its preparations for the broader implementation of energy management systems, FB is currently analysing its energy consumption data and energy certificates within the framework of the SUPERSHINE pilot activities, with support from the tenants themselves, providing pivotal insights on their energy consumption and savings patterns.

Lightning systems and facades

Furthermore, members of FB Department 200 board and four FB staff members, together with ESCO company SUSTAIN SOLUTIONS, are carrying out energy screening for four hundred and fifty households in Department 200 for energy saving measures implementation. This analysis is crucial for understanding the potential of applying energy management systems across its operations. However, the analysis is still ongoing, and no conclusions have yet been drawn regarding the specific opportunities for installing these systems.

Once the analysis is complete, it will serve as a solid foundation for further planning and decision-making regarding the rollout of energy management systems. A key factor in this process will be identifying the most suitable financing mechanisms, an essential step that FB aims to address through the SUPERSHINE pilot activity. Only by securing the right financial solutions can FB move forward with the implementation of these systems, ensuring their sustainability and effectiveness in reducing energy consumption.

Community-shaped future vision of the Faellesbo district

The deep renovation measures undertaken by FB involve a comprehensive overhaul of the building's structure. This includes insulating the walls, roofs, and floors, as well as replacing windows, doors, floors, and updating installations. Additionally, outdoor areas are being renovated to improve the overall environment around the building. These extensive renovation efforts are being financed through a combination of support from Landsbyggefonden and real estate loans, backed by municipal guarantees.

Render of a renovated apartment

The figure presents the render of a renovated apartment showcasing the transformation, reflecting the significant improvements made. The same can be said for the entire building, which, after renovation, stands as a testament to the potential for energy efficiency and aesthetic renewal (the render is shown in the below picture). The outdoor green spaces have also been revitalised, providing residents with a pleasant and sustainable environment.

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Before the renovation, the building faced considerable challenges, including high heat consumption of 120 kWh/m² per year, compounded by issues with mould. However, following the renovation, it is expected that heat consumption will drop dramatically to just 37.0 kWh/m² per year, marking a significant achievement in energy efficiency and improved living conditions for the residents.

Render of an outdoor area among buildings

4.1.2.1. Progress monitoring in SE KPIs achievement

The measurement of Social Engagement indicators for the activities outlined in section 4.1.2 is presented in Table 2. These indicators provide a quantitative assessment of engagement at the demo site, supporting the implementation of the roadmap detailed in D1.2. The activities span Phase 1 (Awareness/Launch) and partially Phase 2 (Design of renovation works) of the roadmap. A distinguishing feature of FællesBo's engagement roadmap is the categorization of activities into four sub-groups: PV (photovoltaic), energy management, re-use of building materials, and re-wilding. In Table 2, each activity is identified by its corresponding sub-category, indicated in square brackets at the start of the description.

The KPI1.SE measurements reveal a high level of engagement overall, although one-third of the activities did not meet the target number of participants. These underperforming activities include one related to PV, two to re-wilding, and one to energy management. While this data does not indicate a specific sub-category that consistently garners less interest from residents, the re-wilding activities warrant closer monitoring. Additionally, KPI2.SE measurements confirm that all key stakeholder groups were effectively reached through the activities. The sole capacity-building initiative, "Training sessions on energy management technologies," successfully engaged all targeted participants.

Table 2: Social Engagement Indicators for FællesBo demo site

KPI code and name	Stakeholder Outreach (KPI1.SE)	Stakeholders Groups (KPI2.SE)	Capacity building activities (KPI4.SE)
KPI definition	This KPI measures the number of stakeholders engaged in the LH for each	This KPI assesses the participation of all stakeholders' groups that the	Number of SHs reached by capacity

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	activity conducted (e.g., co-design sessions, capacity building sessions, community events) according to the target set	activity aims to engage in the event. For instance, if a workshop involving tenants, students and local association has been planned, it is important to verify that all stakeholders' groups have participated.	building activities or material prepared
Unit of measurement	%	%	Number
Engagement activity 1: Questionnaire-focused meeting (11 members of FB organization board)	(8 participants / 11 target) = 73%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 2: Questionnaire-focused meeting (Director and project of FB)	(2 participants / 2 target) = 100%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 3 [PV]: PV systems pilot installation validation and co-decision meeting	(13 participants / 20 target) = 65%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 4 [PV]: Stakeholders' dialogue for financing PV systems	(49 participants / 40 target) = 100%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 5 [RE-USE OF BUILDING MATERIALS]: Stakeholder-led administrative sessions for the construction of an orangery	(35 participants / 35 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 6 [RE-USE OF BUILDING MATERIALS]: Regular meetings to involve students from the Herningsholm Business Academy	(35 participants / 35 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 7 [RE-USE OF BUILDING MATERIALS]: Community-led building of a garden shed and a fireplace	(40 participants / 40 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>

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Engagement activity 8 [RE-USE OF BUILDING MATERIALS]: Involving local SMEs for a sustainable built environment	(4 participants / 4 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	n/a
Engagement activity 9 [RE-WILDING]: Tenants' awareness raising meetings about rewilding (Information and discussion about increasing bio-diversity in common green areas)	(30 participants / 25 target) = 83%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	n/a
Engagement activity 10 [RE-WILDING]: Tenants' awareness raising meetings about rewilding (By re-wilding increasing bio-diversity in FB department 24's green common areas)	(270 participants / 270 target) = 100%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	n/a
Engagement activity 11 [RE-WILDING]: Tenants' awareness raising meetings about rewilding (Up-start meeting for preparing the re-wilding project in FB department 24)	(10 participants / 8 target) = 80%	(5 SH categories participated / 5 target SH) = 100%	n/a
Engagement activity 12 [RE-WILDING]: Tenants' awareness raising meetings about rewilding (Building raised plant beds in FB department 24)	(15 participants / 15 target) = 100%	(4 SH categories participated / 4 target SH) = 100%	n/a
Engagement activity 13 [ENERGY MANAGEMENT] Community-led sessions for identifying financing models for energy management technologies	(5 participants / 7 target) = 71%	(5 SH categories participated / 6 target SH) = 83%	n/a
Engagement activity 14 [ENERGY MANAGEMENT]: Training sessions on energy management technologies	(7 participants / 7 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	7

<p>Engagement activity 15 [ENERGY MANAGEMENT]: Collaborative analysis on energy savings patterns and certificates</p>	<p>(7 participants / 7 target) = 100%</p>	<p>(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%</p>	<p>n/a</p>
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4.1.3. Trieste – Italy

The adopted methodology is rooted in participatory design, applied to the formulation and implementation of *people-centred* local development policies, using facilitation tools such as engagement, listening, co-design, and empowerment. The pathway implemented in the Trieste lighthouse aims at co-designing the collective spaces of the new residential complex on Via Boito, engaging specific target groups. This approach made it possible to identify the needs and aspirations of different categories of residents more precisely and concretely. To encourage participation, meetings have been promoted among residents through personal invitations, word-of-mouth among neighbours, and engagement with local stakeholders, supported by dedicated informational materials distributed within the neighbourhood, at public facilities, and in local businesses. Among these, "Bar Latteria Antonella" has emerged as a key point of reference, thanks to the support of its owner, who has facilitated the dissemination of project initiatives.

The preparatory phase of the project involved constructing the territorial context through stakeholder mapping. This analysis identified key informants and participants to be involved in the participatory pathway. The mapping activity is dynamic and inclusive, aiming to engage institutions and groups, including informal ones, that hold relevant perspectives on the issues being addressed. Furthermore, stakeholder mapping helped monitor which local actors need to be included to ensure the project's development is as comprehensive and integrated as possible. Through these actions, the project positioned itself not only as an urban intervention but also as an opportunity to strengthen the sense of community and promote an active participation model that values every voice and perspective.

The community engagement activities for co-creation and co-decision towards the Boito district renovation are following the designed project strategy and roadmap, provided by ICONS, and directly integrated by ATER with insights from BOITO's needs and wants: currently, the first phase, dedicated to awareness, has been completed, and the second phase, connected to co-design of renovations works, is happening, to be completed by Spring 2025.

Engagement timeline

Kick-off and launch of the activities

The kick-off event in Boito

On 13 June 2024, the launch event of co-design activities was organised with the presence of the community. The institutions and all the stakeholders involved have been presented by ATER, supported by APRE, with the path that will be followed in the upcoming months to maximise the engagement and the direct involvement of the stakeholders, as well as the survey questionnaire to be administered to the population. The redevelopment project of the complex was outlined and presented to the community during the kick-off event, obtaining appreciation from the institutions, trade and professional associations and companies present at the meeting. This event represented a pivotal moment for

connecting with residents was the public presentation of the participatory pathway, as some residents volunteered to inform and invite others within their networks of contacts.

Questionnaire data collection sessions with the community

The questionnaire data collection activities began in July 2024, and was completed by September 2024. For the facilitation of co-design processes on the territory, ATER is being supported by social experts from the Association for Social Promotion 'Kallipolis'.

The co-design activities

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The co-design activities, that are being practically implemented starting from September 2024, have been planned in detail: the meetings will be dedicated to the different population targets, also including younger segments of the local population, and will be followed by a general meeting to return the results, in the presence of all the stakeholders involved in the project.

As a starting point, co-creation sessions are being activated with a focus on the external appearance of buildings, green areas and public spaces, in particular:

Presenting the engagement roadmap for Trieste

- Adult target: 1 meeting dedicated to all citizens, 1 meeting dedicated to resident girls and women.
- Youth target: 1 meeting dedicated to the age group 8-11, 1 meeting dedicated to the age group 12-20.
- Adult target: 1 meeting dedicated to possible beneficiaries of the Microarea, meaning the specific denomination urbanistically given to the district of Boito, with its own peculiarities.
- A co-design session on neighbourhood services will also be activated, with the purpose of “the 15 minutes city”, meaning a plan to transform the connections (not only transportation) inside the neighbourhood in a more efficient and human-centred way.
- Adult target: 1 meeting dedicated to all citizens.

Co-design sessions for future services in the Microarea of Boito

A shot from one of the co-design sessions

In October 2024, SUPERSHINE hosted two engaging co-design sessions for the future services to be implemented in the Microarea of Boito, aimed at fostering collaboration and idea generation among key stakeholders. The first session brought together service providers from neighbouring Microareas, targeting professionals who are already involved in the local ecosystem. The second meeting focused on social gatekeepers, inviting service referents who act as vital intermediaries within the community network.

Both sessions commenced with a comprehensive presentation of the project's goals and the participatory pathway by representatives from

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ATER Trieste and the facilitators from the association for social promotion Kallipolis APS. These introductions set the stage for collaborative discussions that would unfold over the next two hours. The brainstorming sessions, guided by experienced facilitators, encouraged participants to explore key themes and challenges. Stimulus questions were employed to spark conversations and foster collective reasoning, ensuring that the discussions remained both focused and dynamic.

A SWOT analysis board from the event

The primary aim of these sessions was to develop a SWOT analysis and gather innovative ideas for new services that the Microarea initiative could offer to its neighbourhoods. The SWOT analysis served as a strategic tool, shedding light on the intervention's characteristics and its interplay with the surrounding environment. By examining internal factors (strengths and weaknesses) alongside external ones (opportunities and threats), participants were able to align their strategies with achievable objectives. This methodology proved invaluable in identifying controllable variables within the project while also recognising external factors that, although beyond the organisation's direct influence, could be managed or leveraged. By doing so, the team aimed to amplify positive outcomes while mitigating risks that could hinder the initiative's success. The sessions exemplified a structured yet creative approach to participatory planning, paving the way for practical and impactful innovations in community service delivery.

INTERNAL VARIABLES	
Strenghts	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Settlement of New Inhabitants (60 apartments for a total of about 180 inhabitants) - Construction of the new Microarea Headquarters on the ground floor - Presence of Neighborhood Services - Presence of a police station - Opening of the public spaces of the new housing complex to the entire neighborhood - Realization of green facades that will contribute to the "urban status" of the neighborhood and bring beauty - Realization of large multifunctional spaces (community kitchen, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existing establishments have been empty for a long time - Failure of tenants to comply with ATER regulations. - inhabitants target of ATER houses have little care for communal spaces - Lack of sense of belonging to the neighborhood since the settlement of new residents will go by ATER rankings - High dropout rate - Difficulty in maintaining the beauty

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - theater-cinema, library) - Attention to accessibility 	
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EXTERNAL VARIABLES	
Opportunities	Risk (threats)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activation of projects based on the Public-Private Partnership for the management of services - Establishment of a neighborhood board and/or resident committees linked to house numbers - realization of aggregation services for the elderly - realization of a neighborhood library and/or toy library - presence of educational and school services - Presence of services for sports activities - focus intervention for children and young people with an entertainment service for young children to support family management - Reclaiming the neighborhood soccer field - Connection with the Chamber of Commerce Project aimed at encouraging services' activation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New residents will be selected based on the ATER Ranking and therefore cannot be involved in the participatory pathway phase - The Law Enforcement Presidium with the presence of the barracks may hinder the aggregation of the neighborhood, also because of the service that will be activated to dispense the residence permit - Disillusionment of citizens by not delivering what was promised or delivering it in too long a time frame - Resistance on the part of the municipality to promote innovative services - During the uncovered hours of social and educational services, it can be difficult to handle some distressing situations typical of public housing neighborhoods - The figure of the "Head of Household" as representative of the condominium may generate situations of conflict or excessive individualism instead of facilitating the ATER-tenant relationship - The lack of the "family of origin context" can be an impediment to the integration of new tenants - The economic scarcity of families residing in the new complex can be an obstacle to the care and maintenance of the spaces.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - implementing a playground - Maintain and improve public transportation service to the city center (Buses) - Provide several water points (drinking fountains) - Ensuring adequate lighting
<p>Social hub and service “Habitat Microarea”</p>	<p>Suburban neighborhoods need beautiful and welcoming gathering spaces that can also contain innovative services that will also attract citizens living in the city center. Among these we call for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the creation of a public gathering space for the neighborhood such as the <u>“Square”</u> - The activation of a play space both outdoors and indoors such as a toy library dedicated to children, young people but also adults - A free and flexible gathering space both outdoors and indoors, suitable for all ages - the possibility of activating a neighborhood library - enhancement of the after-school service

Elements also emerge that can be considered to cut across all proposals:

- *Intergenerationality*: new spaces and services must be able to meet the needs of children, young people and the elderly.
- *Beauty*: spaces must be of quality and with a focus on design and its forms (i.e., the opposite of the spaces often found in Trieste's predominantly public housing suburbs)
- *Color and art*: the new ATER complex must be able to recall the importance of color, as an antithesis to gray, the color of concrete symbolizing decay and suburban life, and art that can express itself in different ways and that can also involve the new inhabitants.

A journey through the neighbourhood: an exploratory walk for community engagement

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A journey through the neighbourhood event pictures

On a bright Saturday morning of October, an exploratory walk unfolded in the heart of the neighbourhood. This participatory event was designed to bring together residents, stakeholders, and citizens in a shared journey of discovery. Organised with the support of representatives from ATER TS and Kallipolis APS, the walk promised not only insights into the area but also a chance to foster connections among those who call it home.

Leading the group was Mr. Mario Sorz, a long-time resident and devoted historian of the neighbourhood. With his enthusiasm and knowledge, he guided the participants along a thoughtfully planned route, beginning at Via Boito. From there, the group ventured down Via Puccini, visiting landmarks such as the municipal kindergarten "Azzurra," the elementary school G. Foschiatti, the serene Marisa Madieri municipal garden, and the parish church of Jesus Divine Worker. The journey continued, retracing Via Boito to explore the District 3 headquarters of the Azienda Sanitaria, the Acquerello kindergarten on Via Puccini, and finally returning to the Antonella Dairy Bar, where refreshments awaited.

Walking, in this context, served as more than just a mode of transportation. It became a tool for connection and reflection. As the group meandered through the streets, a natural rhythm of conversation emerged. Participants shared observations, posed questions, expressed wishes, and swapped anecdotes about the neighbourhood's history. These informal exchanges brought to light a tapestry of experiences, memories, and ideas, creating a vibrant narrative of the area's identity and potential.

This approach not only strengthened bonds among the participants but also deepened their understanding of the neighbourhood and the proposed projects on the horizon. Through this shared exploration, a sense of community and collaboration flourished. The participants articulated several aspirations and concerns, which underscored the importance of thoughtful redevelopment:

- **Revitalising spaces:** There was a clear call for both outdoor and indoor spaces to foster social interaction across all age groups.
- **Enhancing green areas:** The need for communal green spaces where children could play safely, free from the dangers of traffic, was strongly voiced.

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- **Preserving essential services:** Many emphasised the importance of maintaining and expanding local services to prevent the neighbourhood from becoming a dormitory zone.
- **Encouraging innovation:** Participants envisioned aesthetically pleasing, innovative spaces designed to facilitate community gatherings.

In essence, the walk was more than just a stroll through familiar streets. It was a step towards a collective vision, a dialogue on how to preserve and enhance the neighbourhood while ensuring it remains a vibrant and inclusive space for all.

Other shots of the day

Future vision of the Boito district

Overview of the New ATER Residential Complex in Via Boito (Render, Map)

As mentioned above, ATER Trieste plans to demolish and rebuild the buildings in the district of Boito, to overcome their functional obsolescence, their state of deterioration, as well as the technological inadequacy, with an organic series of redevelopment and renovation interventions, co-created with the neighbouring communities and the local Association for Social Promotion 'Kallipolis' as facilitator.

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The architectural and urban planning project of the new ATER residential complex in Via Boito is set to redefine sustainable living with its innovative design and focus on energy efficiency. Comprised of seven modern buildings, it introduces fifty-six additional apartments tailored to contemporary lifestyles. Each structure is equipped with advanced energy-saving technologies, including photovoltaic panels that harness clean energy and systems for heat recovery, ensuring minimal environmental impact.

Green Houses classes A0 & A+

Render of one of the future buildings in Boito

Residents will benefit from a range of collective amenities, including accessible association spaces and vibrant green recreational areas. Urban and vertical gardens bring nature closer, while water recovery systems and blue-green roofs enhance ecological resilience. Designed with acoustic comfort in mind, the complex provides a peaceful living environment amidst the hustle of city life.

This ambitious project also opens the door to the creation of an energy community, empowering residents to share and manage resources sustainably. It's a vision of modern living where innovation meets environmental responsibility.

4.1.3.1. Progress monitoring in SE KPIs achievement

Table 3 below presents the Social Engagement indicators measured for the activities in Trieste described in section 4.1.3. The implementation of D1.2 roadmap at the demo sites spans cover Phase 1: Awareness/Launch of activities and the first part of Phase 2: Design of renovations works as planned on the demo site engagement roadmap in D1.2.

With the exception of the project kick-off meeting, all activities fall under Phase 2 and focus on co-design processes. Participation levels were consistently high, with the kick-off meeting serving as the primary opportunity to gather informed feedback and generate ideas for renovation efforts. A review of KPI1.SE and KPI2.SE measurements highlights strong outreach and engagement across co-creation activities, confirming that all target stakeholder groups actively participated in the co-design process as planned.

Measuring these indicators, alongside comparisons with Social Awareness indicators, provides valuable feedback that can help adjust and refine planned activities at the demo site. Since the kick-

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off activity did not engage all target stakeholder categories, as indicated by KPI2.SE, future activities could benefit from incorporating awareness-raising components or introducing new informational initiatives. This need for adjustment is reinforced by KPI2.SA measurements from the Social Awareness indicators in section 4.2.2.3, which highlight a relatively low level of resident awareness about the SUPERSHINE project.

Table 3: Social Engagement Indicators for Trieste demo site

KPI code and name	Stakeholder Outreach (KPI1.SE)	Stakeholders Groups (KPI2.SE)
KPI definition	This KPI measures the number of stakeholders engaged in the LH for each activity conducted (e.g., co-design sessions, capacity building sessions, community events) according to the target set	This KPI assesses the participation of all stakeholders' groups that the activity aims to engage in the event. For instance, if a workshop involving tenants, students and local association has been planned, it is important to verify that all stakeholders' groups have participated.
Unit of measurement	%	%
Kick of meeting of the project	(49 participants / 35 target) = 140%	(6 SH categories participated / 8 target SH) = 75%
Engagement Activity 6 - Co-design session 1	(13 participants / 12 target) = 108%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%
Engagement Activity 7 - Co-design session 2	(13 participants / 12 target) = 108%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%
Engagement Activity 8 - Co-design session 3	(13 participants / 12 target) = 108%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%

4.2. Social Acceptance Analysis and Monitoring

4.2.1. Overview of the Questionnaire and the Social Acceptance Indicators

In Task 1.2, the project aimed at assessing its impact on social acceptance and engagement regarding the proposed interventions, employing a comprehensive evaluation framework based on specific KPIs, detailed in **D1.2 – Engagement Strategy and Social Acceptance KPIs**. These KPIs were carefully crafted using both top-down and bottom-up approaches. The top-down approach drew extensively from established academic literature and theoretical frameworks, such as Technology Acceptance Models (TAM) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT).

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These models, particularly in the context of urban regeneration, addressed factors such as Quality of Life, Attractiveness, Perceived Benefits (e.g., comfort and well-being), Aesthetics and Social Image, and Perceived Usefulness. A thorough review of these models and associated empirical research provided a robust foundation for understanding how individuals and communities adopted various solutions. Nonetheless, their focus on information systems posed limitations, necessitating the introduction of new indicators tailored to the unique attributes of the SUPERSHINE project. Complementing this, the bottom-up approach focused on aligning the KPIs with the project's technical and social objectives, reflecting the specific goals and characteristics of all lighthouse representatives.

Development process for the KPIs definition

While the analysis of the engagement KPIs was carried out in the above paragraphs **4.1.1.1**, **4.1.2.1**, and **4.1.3.1**, as they are directly connected to the engagement activities implemented up to date by each lighthouse with their respective communities, to measure the Social Acceptance KPIs a specific questionnaire was created, adapted together with the lighthouse managers to the context of each lighthouse, and whose template is exhibited in **Annex 2**.

List of Social Acceptance Indicators

- KPI1.SA Changing Attitudes
- KPI2.SA Awareness
- KPI3.SA Perceived value for money
- KPI4.SA Perceived usefulness
- KPI5.SA Quality of Life
- KPI6.SA Perceived ease of use
- KPI7.SA Social Image
- KPI8.SA Aesthetic Value
- KPI9.SA Perceived Comfort
- KPI10.SA Bill saving
- KPI11.SA Sense of belonging
- KPI12.SA Green Areas

The questionnaire was administered during 2024, with different timing for each lighthouse, to collect the baseline data, and will be administered again in mid-2025, at the end of the engagement activities, to understand how the endline data will be influenced by the inspiring principle of the SUPERSHINE social acceptance model, namely "awareness through engagement", aiming at obtaining increased awareness and acceptability through direct involvement and engagement of the communities, in particular through community-led co-design and co-decision of solutions, increasing their sense of ownership for the intended process of renovation of neighbourhoods. In the figure, an overview of the Social Acceptance KPIs, each of which has been associated with one of the three pillars of the NEB, either "Beautiful", "Sustainable", or "Together".

4.2.2. Analysis of baseline data for Social Acceptance KPIs achievement

The following sections - 4.2.2.1 for Riga, 4.2.2.2 for FællesBo and 4.2.2.3 for Trieste - disclose the measurement of Social Acceptance indicators in the SUPERSHINE demo sites. This data was collected through the questionnaire reported in Annex 2, which was tailored to each demo site characteristics in collaboration with demo site leaders. The tailoring included possible removal or slight modifications of questions, and translation in the local language. The actual questions asked to respondents are reported above each KPI measurement, translated in English. As planned in the respective engagement roadmaps of demo sites, data collection was carried out before the start of renovation works and therefore it is not influenced by the latter.

The data collected constitutes the baseline reference for understanding the context in the demo sites, which will be compared with data collected through the same questionnaires after the renovation works. As defined in the D1.2 monitoring framework, the comparison between the two sets of data will allow to identify the impact of the SUPERSHINE interventions on the social perception of the communities in the demo sites..

4.2.2.1. Riga

The indicator KPI1.SA aims at assessing the attitude to change on energy patterns in the pilots; the measurements reported above constitute the baseline situation in Riga pilot, which will be compared to data collected after SUPERSHINE interventions. The overall assessment of the pilot reveals a mixed landscape. While a significant portion of respondents recognize the effectiveness of energy measures, a notable percentage remain unconvinced. In response to the first question, 64% of participants do not fully identify as adopting energy conservation behaviours. This is likely linked to a lack of awareness regarding what such behaviours entail, as 42% of these responses were "neutral."

Regarding the effectiveness of renewable energy sources, 47% of respondents either disagree or strongly disagree, suggesting a potential lack of trust in this area. This highlights the need for engagement efforts to prioritize raising awareness and enhancing residents' understanding of the diverse applications and benefits of energy measures, with particular emphasis on renewable energy. Gathering more qualitative data could provide deeper insights into these responses. Conversely, attitudes towards recycling and waste reduction are more positive, with 52% of respondents strongly agreeing and 16% agreeing on the importance of these practices. This indicates that recycling and waste reduction are the least contentious aspects of the sustainability transition.

"I contribute to conserving energy by practicing habits such as turning off lights when not in use, unplugging electronics, and reducing unnecessary energy consumption."

(KPI1.SA)

"Utilizing alternative sources of energy, such as solar or wind power, can significantly reduce our reliance on traditional energy sources, like fossil fuels. By harnessing renewable resources, we can decrease our carbon footprint, mitigate environmental impact, and promote a more sustainable energy future."

(KPI1.SA)

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Figure 1: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

Figure 2: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

"By reusing items, recycling materials, and minimizing waste generation, not only helps preserve natural resources and protect the environment but also promotes safe energy practices. By reducing the need for energy-intensive manufacturing processes we can conserve energy resources, minimize pollution, and create a safer and more sustainable energy ecosystem for future generations."

(KPI1.SA)

Figure 3: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

The level of awareness concerning SUPERSHINE project is not unsatisfactory; it must be noted however that some activities were already carried out in the pilot at the moment of data collection, limiting the amount data collected. From this perspective, the fact that that two-thirds of respondents are either not completely aware or unaware about the project suggests that more efforts should be done to increase the level of awareness about the SUPERSHINE project in the community. Regarding the evaluation of the investment’s value to the community, the majority of respondents view it as worthwhile. Only 10% of responses indicate that the investment is perceived as somewhat or completely unworthy.

"Are you aware of the ongoing interventions of the SUPERSHINE project?"

(KPI2.SA)

"To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as being worth the investment made in your community?"

(KPI3.SA)

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Figure 4: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

Figure 5: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

Considering the preliminary evaluation of interventions by respondents, the later overwhelmingly agree on the useful impact of interventions on energy sustainability in the pilot. Baseline data on the demo site's context reveals that 78% of respondents agree the site already has a positive social image.

“To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices?”

(KPI4.SA)

“How do you perceive the social image projected by the community?”

(KPI7.SA)

Figure 6: Perceived Usefulness (KPI4.SA)

Figure 7: Social image (KPI7.SA)

Aligning with KPI7.SA reported above, 77% of respondents already appreciate the aesthetics of the buildings as Figure 8 shows.

“What is your perception on the aesthetics of the buildings?”

(KPI8.SA)

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Figure 8: Aesthetic value (KPI8.SA)

As Figure 9 and 10 show, the satisfaction with temperatures of interiors varies greatly between seasons. While the winter temperatures are appreciated by the majority of residents, only 13% of residents report being slightly satisfied or unsatisfied overall. However, when it comes to summer temperatures, the percentage of respondents who are only slightly satisfied rises to 65%. This suggests lower appreciation of temperature comfort during summer, though it does not indicate significant discomfort.

"How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during winter?"

(KPI9.SA)

"How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during summer?"

(KPI9.SA)

Figure 9: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

Figure 10: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

As Figure 11 and 12 shows, the indicator concerning reduction of energy bills signal a high degree of expectation on a reduction in energy expenditure, with 77% of respondents believing interventions are going to have a relevant impact on their bills. Observing instead the answers concerning the perception of being integrated through community building activities, respondents are less unanimous: importantly, 6% of respondents feel not at all integrated and 26% only slightly, pointing out the need to further engage residents in activities that also have community building purposes. It would also be valuable to conduct qualitative research to understand the reasons behind these responses from one-third of the respondents.

"Do you believe that the project interventions can contribute to reduce your energy bills?"

"To what extent do you feel integrated as part of the community as a result of the project interventions?"

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(KPI10.SA)

Figure 11: Bill saving (KPI10.SA)

(KPI11.SA)

Figure 12: Sense of belonging (KPI11.SA)

The use of green public spaces in the pilot is quite high, with 59% of respondents reporting that they use the spaces every day or at least often.

“How often do you use your green spaces and communal spaces within your block?”

(KPI12.SA)

Figure 13: Green Areas (KPI12.SA)

The use of green public spaces in the pilot is quite high, with 59% of respondents reporting that they use the spaces every day or at least often.

4.2.2.2. Herning – Denmark

As Figure 14 and 15 show, given the role of respondents as residents’ representatives and their small number, the answers concerning awareness about SUPERSHINE project are not completely satisfactory, with 38% of respondents giving “neutral” feedback on their awareness about the project. The level of awareness among this category of stakeholders should be quite high, so that in turn they can inform and raise the awareness of residents. Nevertheless, all respondents agree on perceiving the renovation as worthy, pointing out the latter as uncontroversial.

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“Are you aware of the ongoing interventions of the SUPERSHINE project?”

(KPI2.SA)

Figure 14: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

“To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as being worth the investment made in your community?”

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 15: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

The interventions are perceived by respondents as highly promising in promoting sustainability in the pilot, with no apparent doubts as Figures 16 and 17 show. Respondents also agree upon the positive impact on the quality of life of residents, even though it would be interesting to collect qualitative data on the reasons for the lower degree of agreement shared by one of the respondents.

“To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices?”

(KPI4.SA)

Figure 16: Perceived Usefulness (KPI4.SA)

“To what extent do you perceive the efforts as beneficial for the residents' general quality of life?”

(KPI5.SA)

Figure 17: Quality of life (KPI5.SA)

Perceptions of the user-friendliness of solutions are generally high. However, the 38% of respondents who selected “slightly” indicate the need to monitor this aspect during future engagement activities with residents as Figure 18 shows. In terms of the community’s perceived social image, one-third of respondents do not view it as clearly positive (Figure 19).

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“To what extent do you perceive the deployed technologies, such as control panels and thermostats, as user-friendly and easy to operate?”

(KPI6.SA)

Figure 18: User experience: Perceived ease of use (KPI6.SA)

“How do you perceive the social image projected by the community?”

(KPI7.SA)

Figure 19: Social image (KPI7.SA)

As Figure 20 shows, unlike KPI7.SA on social image, the aesthetic of the buildings is not seen as an issue, with respondents expressing unanimous appreciation.

“What is your perception on the aesthetics of the buildings?”

(KPI8.SA)

Figure 20: Aesthetic value (KPI8.SA)

The evaluation of temperature comfort appears inconsistent and varies by season (Figure 21 and 22). In winter, a notable 50% of respondents report being only slightly satisfied, highlighting the need to investigate the factors contributing to this lukewarm perception of comfort. In contrast, summer temperature comfort is more widely appreciated; however, none of the respondents express a very high level of satisfaction, indicating room for improvement even during warmer months.

“How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during winter?”

“How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during summer?”

D1.3 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 1

(KPI9.SA)

Figure 21: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

(KPI9.SA)

Figure 22: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

All respondents share positive expectations regarding the anticipated impact of interventions on reducing energy bills, reflecting a high level of optimism (Figure 23). However, perceptions of community integration through community-building activities are less unanimous (Figure 24). This warrants further investigation, as all respondents are tenant representatives, suggesting that existing dynamics of integration may already be at play within the pilot.

“Do you believe that the project interventions can contribute to reduce your energy bills?”

(KPI10.SA)

Figure 23: Bill saving (KPI10.SA)

“To what extent do you feel integrated as part of the community as a result of the project interventions?”

(KPI11.SA)

Figure 24: Sense of belonging (KPI11.SA)

As Figure 25 shows, the use of green spaces seems to be not extremely frequent among all residents: nevertheless, one-quarter of respondents report to go into the green spaces every day, signalling the possible existence of a sub-group of residents that have an intense use of the green areas.

“How often do you use your green spaces and communal spaces within your block?”

(KPI12.SA)

Figure 25: Green Areas (KPI12.SA)

4.2.2.3. Trieste – Italy

The responses to KPI1.SA (Figure 28) provide insight into the willingness to adopt new energy practices at the Trieste pilot site. While the vast majority of respondents report actively contributing to sustainability measures, this majority diminishes when evaluating perceptions of the positive impact of renewable energy sources and recycling practices. Notably, the highest number of "neutral" or disagreeing responses relate to renewable energy.

These results suggest that approximately one-third of respondents may lack sufficient information about sustainability measures, particularly regarding renewable energy sources. Targeted engagement activities that also focus on raising awareness and providing information on renewables could help bridge this knowledge gap.

"I contribute to conserving energy by practicing habits such as turning off lights when not in use, unplugging electronics, and reducing unnecessary energy consumption."

(KPI1.SA)

"Utilizing alternative sources of energy, such as solar or wind power, can significantly reduce our reliance on traditional energy sources, like fossil fuels. By harnessing renewable resources, we can decrease our carbon footprint, mitigate environmental impact, and promote a more sustainable energy future."

(KPI1.SA)

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Figure 26: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

Figure 27: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

"By reusing items, recycling materials, and minimizing waste generation, not only helps preserve natural resources and protect the environment but also promotes safe energy practices. By reducing the need for energy-intensive manufacturing processes we can conserve energy resources, minimize pollution, and create a safer and more sustainable energy ecosystem for future generations."

(KPI1.SA)

Figure 28: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

The KPI2.SA indicator (Figure 29), which measures residents' awareness of SUPERSHINE interventions, reflects very low levels of awareness. This underscores the urgent need to incorporate more informational components into engagement activities and potentially organize dedicated sessions to address this gap. In contrast, the indicator measuring perceptions of renovation value (Figure 30) shows more positive results, with 69% of respondents viewing the renovations as worthwhile. However, given the high number of respondents, it would be valuable to investigate the reasons behind the 16% who deemed the renovations unworthy, as their perspectives represent a significant portion of the polled population.

"Are you aware of the ongoing interventions of the SUPERSHINE project?"

"To what extent do you perceive the houses renovation as being worth the investment?"

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(KPI2.SA)

Figure 29: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 30: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

As Figure 31 shows, most respondents generally perceive SUPERSHINE interventions as effective in promoting sustainability: however, 10% express scepticism or potential doubt. This scepticism increases to 18% when evaluating the perceived benefits of the interventions on residents' quality of life as Figure 32 shows, with these respondents rating the impact as either "Poor" or "Very Poor." "These results suggest a potential lack of trust in the interventions, highlighting the need to address concerns through future engagement activities focused on building confidence and demonstrating tangible benefits to residents.

"To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices?"

(KPI4.SA)

Figure 31: Perceived Usefulness (KPI4.SA)

"To what extent do you perceive the efforts as beneficial for the residents' general quality of life?"

(KPI5.SA)

Figure 32: Quality of life (KPI5.SA)

The scepticism reflected in the KPI5.SA measurement is further validated by KPI6.SA as Figure 33 shows. This indicator, which assesses perceived ease of use, reveals that 21% of respondents do not find the interventions user-friendly. Addressing this issue will be essential during Phase 4 (Handover) of the roadmap, with a focus on capacity-building activities. Special attention should be given to ensuring that non-expert users can easily understand and engage with the interventions.

D1.3 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 1

“To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices?”

(KPI6.SA)

Figure 33: User experience: Perceived ease of use (KPI6.SA)

The KPIs evaluating social image and aesthetic appreciation show relatively low results, likely reflecting the current abandoned and run-down state of the pilot site. KPI7.SA, which measures social image (Figure 34), indicates that only 44% of respondents provided a clearly positive assessment of the district's current social perception. Perceptions of building aesthetics are even lower (Figure 35), with 62% of respondents finding the buildings either unappealing or very unappealing. A significant improvement in the appreciation of the buildings is anticipated following the SUPERSHINE interventions.

“How do you perceive the social image projected by the community?”

(KPI7.SA)

“What is your perception on the aesthetics of the buildings?”

(KPI8.SA)

Figure 34: Social image (KPI7.SA)

Figure 35: Aesthetic value (KPI8.SA)

The evaluation of temperature comfort highlights clear satisfaction with winter conditions (Figure 36). In this case, 52% of respondents report being fully satisfied, while 34% express moderate satisfaction with winter temperatures. However, satisfaction levels drop notably during summer

D1.3 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 1

(Figure 37). Only 38% of respondents are satisfied, and 25% report moderate satisfaction. A significant portion, the 36%, are either slightly satisfied or dissatisfied, indicating a need to address summer temperature comfort through targeted improvements.

"How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during winter?"

(KPI9.SA)

Figure 36: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

"How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during summer?"

(KPI9.SA)

Figure 37: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

Respondents' expectations regarding the impact of interventions on energy bills are mixed (Figure 38), with nearly one-third expressing some level of scepticism. Future engagement activities should prioritize clearly demonstrating the financial savings achieved through SUPERSHINE interventions. KPI11.SA, which measures the effectiveness of community-building activities, reveals that 66% of respondents feel little to no sense of integration from these activities. However, it is important to note that community-building efforts have yet to be fully implemented at the pilot site. These results underscore the need to place significant focus on developing and enhancing community-building initiatives as a key component of future engagement efforts.

"Do you believe that the project interventions can contribute to reduce your energy bills?"

(KPI10.SA)

Figure 38: Bill saving (KPI10.SA)

"To what extent do you feel integrated as part of the community because of the community building activities?"

(KPI11.SA)

Figure 39: Sense of belonging (KPI11.SA)

The use of green spaces by residents appears consistent but infrequent as Figure 40 shows. Only 20% of respondents report using these spaces daily or regularly.

“How often do you use your green spaces and communal spaces within your block?”

(KPI12.SA)

Figure 40: Green Areas (KPI12.SA)

The social acceptance analysis highlights a nuanced landscape of resident perceptions and engagement with the SUPERSHINE interventions. While there is strong recognition of the value of sustainability measures and general optimism about the impact on energy bills, scepticism remains, particularly regarding renewable energy sources and temperature comfort during summer. The low levels of awareness and engagement reflected in key performance indicators emphasize the need for more targeted informational and capacity-building activities. Community-building efforts, still in their early stages, will require dedicated attention to foster greater integration and trust among residents. Additionally, the aesthetic improvements anticipated through renovations are expected to address concerns about the current state of the pilot site. Overall, the analysis underscores the importance of transparent communication, demonstrable benefits, and inclusive engagement to enhance social acceptance and ensure the long-term success of the interventions.

5. Replicability inputs from the fellow cities

D5.3 - Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities - Part 1, due for M26 like this document, includes the preliminary variables to create a blueprint of the SUPERSHINE social acceptance model for the four fellow cities, Belgrade (Serbia), Zaragoza (Spain), Setúbal (Portugal), and Istanbul (Turkey). The document summarises the methodology and most significant variables used by ICONS to develop the SUPERSHINE social acceptance through engagement model, with the creation of both Social Acceptance and Social Engagement KPIs.

These vertical pillars will be matched in the second part of the deliverable (**D5.4 - Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities - Part 2**) with the horizontal variables of social engagement and acceptance of the fellow cities, whose context framework is traced in D5.3 thanks to the analysis of data collected with the support of fellow cities managers through a short survey on the current status of both social acceptance and community engagement.

These data were integrated with the results of a co-creation workshop held during the annual consortium meeting of SUPERSHINE in November 2024, in which DEMIR, D5.3 leader, arranged a dialogue between the representatives of the three SUPERSHINE lighthouses with those of the fellow cities, in order to promote knowledge and best practice exchange. Below, some images of the boards resulting from the activity.

D1.3 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 1

In-progress replicability suggestions boards for the SUPERSHINE fellow cities

6. Key Takeaway Aspects

Through its carefully structured engagement processes, SUPERSHINE has laid the groundwork for creating sustainable and vibrant communities in its three Lighthouses, so to align with the New European Bauhaus principles of beauty, sustainability, and inclusivity. It can be argued that one of the most promising of SUPERSHINE's strengths lies in its adaptability, demonstrated through the participatory pathways tailored to the unique circumstances of each lighthouse.

In **Riga**, the goal to improve social engagement in the Āgenskalna Priedes district, considering the cultural and socio-economic barriers explained in Section 1, was addressed through targeted and inclusive strategies: multilingual communication was prioritised, with resources provided in both Latvian and Russian to address linguistic barriers. Forums and workshops included hands-on elements that allowed residents to better understand the benefits and processes of energy efficiency projects. Specific efforts were made to reach elderly residents, such as offline materials or in-person assistance, to help bridge the digital divide. Misconceptions about energy efficiency, such as fears of mould formation or doubts about the necessity of insulation, were actively addressed.

Educational campaigns focused on the tangible benefits of renovations, such as improved comfort, cost savings, and long-term building safety, to support perception shifting. Transparent communication about funding mechanisms, particularly EU and municipal grants, alleviated concerns about financial impacts. By fostering collaboration among residents, housing associations, and municipal agencies, and by leveraging existing initiatives like the OSS, Āgenskalna Priedes built a stronger, more engaged community.

More specifically, the Āgenskalna Priedes district exemplified a multi-layered approach to engagement, where the co-design process leveraged on digital platforms like Tandeems and physical workshops to engage residents in envisioning energy-efficient renovations: this hybrid approach underscored the potential of combining traditional community meetings with modern technological tools to widen the scope of participation, including architectural visualisations and participatory budgeting, thus providing residents with a tangible sense of ownership over the refurbishment process.

In fact, the community was involved in activities ranging from neighbourhood festivals to workshops on energy retrofits: these events, coupled with the use of the Tandeems platform, fostered transparency and inclusivity, while the progression from awareness-raising to co-design workshops demonstrated a strategic approach to cultivating long-term community involvement.

In **Herning**, in order to address persistent cultural and social barriers, transparent and inclusive communication strategies were deemed vital during the implementation of the SUPERSHINE engagement model. Clear and consistent updates on renovation timelines, benefits, and measures to minimise disruptions were provided to help build trust and gain support among tenants. For instance, the nearly 50% reduction in energy consumption and the associated long-term cost savings were highlighted to make the benefits more tangible. The planned introduction of Neogrid Smart Energy Management technology presented an opportunity to engage residents by enabling them to monitor and optimise their energy usage. However, this initiative required culturally sensitive training programmes to ensure accessibility for all tenants, including those with limited language proficiency or technical skills.

D1.3 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 1

Collaboration with local stakeholders, such as ESCOs, SMEs, and community leaders, was also critical in fostering engagement. These partnerships supported the co-design of district activities and created opportunities for broader community involvement. Cultural inclusion remained a priority, with efforts made to address language barriers, provide multilingual resources, and involve minority groups in decision-making processes. By building on existing community structures and addressing those cultural challenges, the Fællesbo district succeeded in creating a more inclusive and engaged community, ensuring the success of its energy efficiency initiatives.

Indeed, the lighthouse of Herning capitalised on Denmark's tenant democracy, profoundly merged with the communities cultural fabric, fostering a deep sense of collaboration between tenants and housing authorities, characterising its engagement pathway with the integration of tenant-led initiatives and stakeholder dialogues. The emphasis on co-decision-making ensured a choral approach across a broad spectrum of activities, from selecting energy management technologies to designing community-based recycling labs: this participatory model not only strengthened social cohesion but also embedded sustainability into the community's ethos. The district's emphasis on energy management technologies and material recycling showcases how technical expertise and community input can intersect effectively. Furthermore, it should be pointed out how the involvement of vocational school students in construction projects highlights the significance of education in reinforcing sustainable practices and community resilience.

In **Trieste**, to overcome the socio-cultural barriers perpetually met towards renovation processes, a multi-faceted approach to social engagement was regarded as necessary. Community meetings and workshops, supported by local stakeholders such as the Municipality of Trieste and ATER Trieste, served as platforms for educating residents about the benefits of energy efficiency. Multilingual materials and visual guides were essential in ensuring accessibility for all people involved.

Furthermore, involving residents in co-designing public spaces and energy-saving measures fostered a sense of ownership and trust. Addressing cultural concerns directly, such as fears of cost increases and disruptions, required transparent communication about the long-term financial and comfort benefits of these renovations. By prioritising these efforts, the Boito district created a more engaged and informed community, ensuring the success of its redevelopment plan.

Indeed, social engagement was marked by a deliberate effort to bridge the gap between immediate needs and long-term aspirations. The co-creation sessions mostly focused on addressing the district's urgent need for modernisation, that should be implemented without overlooking upon communities' instances. By involving residents in workshops to redesign public spaces and incorporate green infrastructure, the project created a vision that is both inspirational and achievable, including practical services that should go hand in hand with the concrete renovation of the district.

Workshops focusing on aesthetic and functional redesigns of buildings and public spaces provided a platform for diverse voices, including younger residents and local artists: the integration of artistic and cultural elements further enriched the participatory process, thus strengthening the community's connection to its transformed environment, as well as ensuring that the transformation reflects the community's collective identity and aspirations.

SUPERSHINE's robust monitoring framework aims at ensuring that the effectiveness of engagement strategies is continuously evaluated, while social Acceptance KPIs provided valuable insights into the community's evolving perceptions. For instance, in Riga, the baseline data highlighted areas

D1.3 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 1

(e.g., different uses and outputs of energy measures, with especially renewables) where awareness about energy efficiency needed reinforcement, guiding subsequent workshops and activities.

In Herring, the structured feedback mechanisms, including questionnaires administered through tenant boards, revealed high levels of acceptance and enthusiasm for sustainable interventions. This feedback loop not only validated the project's approach but also identified opportunities for improvement, such as addressing concerns about the economic feasibility of photovoltaic installations.

Trieste's emphasis on post-intervention analysis ensures that the social and environmental impact of renovations is comprehensively understood. The use of surveys to gauge resident satisfaction and the effectiveness of training sessions on energy-efficient technologies underscores the importance of aligning project outcomes with community expectations.

The SUPERSHINE project demonstrates that successful social housing refurbishment requires more than just technical solutions, as it demands a holistic approach that places communities at the centre. By fostering participatory processes, SUPERSHINE not only enhances the physical infrastructure of social housing but also strengthens the social fabric of its communities. The project's alignment with the NEB principles provides a blueprint for creating living environments that are not only sustainable and beautiful but also inclusive and empowering, focusing on the following key takeaway aspects:

- SUPERSHINE's participatory pathways highlight the transformative potential of involving residents in every stage of the refurbishment process. This approach fosters a sense of ownership and ensures that interventions align with community needs and aspirations.
- The use of digital tools, such as Riga's Tandeems platform, illustrates how technology can enhance engagement and streamline co-design processes. Similarly, Herring's exploration of energy management systems underscores the role of innovation in achieving sustainability goals.
- By incorporating cultural heritage and social cohesion into its strategies, SUPERSHINE ensures that its interventions resonate deeply with the communities it serves. Trieste's focus on aesthetic and functional redesigns exemplifies this integration.
- The lessons learned from each lighthouse provide a valuable framework for scaling up and adapting SUPERSHINE's methodologies to other European contexts. The emphasis on innovative financing models and stakeholder collaboration ensures that these strategies are both practical and impactful.

As SUPERSHINE moves forward, its commitment to sustainability, inclusivity, and beauty serves as a testament to the transformative power of community-driven social housing refurbishment. By working deeply at the community level, SUPERSHINE is being allowed to engage stakeholders across the value chain of its envisioned solutions, with a particular focus on enhancing the well-being of frequently overlooked segments of the population. This process is centred on listening directly to communities and providing them instruments to participate and to contribute to paving their future. Indeed, the targeted population in the three SUPERSHINE pilots has previously reported, during the background research, of their difficulties encountered in negotiating with the government traditional forms of top-down funding schemes. Therefore, the communities have begun providing inputs and suggestions, in order to properly customise their respective lighthouse business models to their

D1.3 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 1

specific needs, that vary from country to country. Furthermore, they are being involved in validating and exploring the potential of the innovative financing schemes suggested by the project.

Involving local authorities in the engagement activities, as well as public and private urban planners, while also putting them in direct contact with the communities on an equal level of discussion, is encouraging enhancing multilevel and participatory models of governance, as well as more inclusive and transparent urban planning, enforcing regulations for safety and improved working conditions, e.g., at construction sites (starting from Social LCA results), and incentivising gender and marginalised categories inclusion (e.g., using local association for social promotion and gender equality as facilitators in engaging them, or using both digital and physical meeting formats to allow a wider participation, despite different mobility conditions). In addition, putting cities and communities in connection with European Research & Innovation actors is creating a path to strengthen international action and collaboration for an active community-led Green Transition throughout the EU.

By bridging technical innovation with social awareness, the project not only aims at redefining the possibilities of urban living but also at paving the way for a more equitable and sustainable future across Europe: the success of this goal will be explored in the second part of the deliverable, where the impact of SUPERSHINE solutions in the demo sites on the communities' perception towards integrated energy-efficient renovations will be analysed by comparing the KPIs baseline data with the endline monitoring.

7. Conclusions

SUPERSHINE exemplifies how community-driven engagement can transform social housing refurbishment, aligning with the New European Bauhaus principles of beauty, sustainability, and inclusivity. Across Riga, Herning, and Trieste, the project successfully addressed socio-cultural barriers through participatory design, multilingual communication, and inclusive outreach. By leveraging digital tools, fostering tenant-led initiatives, and integrating artistic and educational elements, SUPERSHINE strengthened social cohesion and empowered residents to take ownership of the refurbishment process. The project's robust monitoring framework ensures continuous adaptation and improvement, highlighting the importance of transparent communication and long-term community involvement. SUPERSHINE's holistic approach serves as a scalable model for sustainable urban renewal, demonstrating that meaningful engagement and collaboration are essential to achieving lasting environmental and social impact.

8. Annexes

8.1. Annex 1

Kristapa 18 “before renovation” Energy Performance Certificate (EPC)

Ēkas energosertifikāts																																																									
REGISTRĀCIJAS NUMURS	BIS-ĒED-1-2017-235																																																								
DERĪGS LĪDZ	27.02.2027																																																								
1. Ēkas veids	daudzdzīvokļu māja																																																								
2.1 Adrese	Rīga, Kristapa iela 18																																																								
3.1 Ēkas daļa	-																																																								
4.1 Ēkas vai tās daļas (telpu grupas) kadastra apzīmējums	01000602021001																																																								
5. Ēkas energosertificēšanas nolūks	pārdošana [], izīrēšana/iznomāšana [], brīvprātīgi [X], valsts/pašvaldības publiska ēka []																																																								
6. Ēkas raksturojums	Pirmreizējais ekspluatācijā pieņemšanas gads: 1959. Pārbūves/Lietošanas veida maiņas/Atjaunošanas gads: - Stāvu skaits: 5 virszemes, 1 pazemes, [] mansards, [] jumta stāvs Kopējā platība: 0.00 m ² Aprēķina platība: 2182.30 m ²																																																								
7. Ēkas energoefektivitātes novērtējums	<table border="0"> <thead> <tr> <th>Atsauces vērtības</th> <th>Ēkas energoefektivitātes klase un rādītājs</th> <th>Ēkas energoefektivitātes rādītāji</th> <th></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td></td> <td style="text-align: center;">0</td> <td>Enerģijas patēriņa novērtējums</td> <td>kWh/m² gadā</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Gandrīz nulles enerģijas ēkas aplūses rādītājs 40</td> <td style="text-align: center;">50</td> <td>apkurei</td> <td>179.10</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td style="text-align: center;">100</td> <td>karstā ūdens sagatavošanai</td> <td>34.70</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td style="text-align: center;">150</td> <td>mehāniskajai ventilācijai</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td style="text-align: center;">200</td> <td>apgaismojumam</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ēkas veidam atbilstošais ēkas vidējais patēriņš 152.04</td> <td style="text-align: center;">179²</td> <td>dzesēšanai</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td style="text-align: center;">250</td> <td>papildu</td> <td>2.50</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Normatīviem atbilstošā ēka -</td> <td style="text-align: center;">300+</td> <td>Patēriņš kopā</td> <td>216.30</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>No atjaunojamiem energoresursiem ēkā sarabotā vai iegūtā enerģija</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Kogenerācijā sarabotā enerģija</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Primārās enerģijas novērtējums</td> <td>281.60</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Oglekļa dioksīda emisijas novērtējums</td> <td>56.69</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>kg CO₂/m² gadā</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Atsauces vērtības	Ēkas energoefektivitātes klase un rādītājs	Ēkas energoefektivitātes rādītāji			0	Enerģijas patēriņa novērtējums	kWh/m ² gadā	Gandrīz nulles enerģijas ēkas aplūses rādītājs 40	50	apkurei	179.10		100	karstā ūdens sagatavošanai	34.70		150	mehāniskajai ventilācijai	0.00		200	apgaismojumam	0.00	Ēkas veidam atbilstošais ēkas vidējais patēriņš 152.04	179 ²	dzesēšanai	0.00		250	papildu	2.50	Normatīviem atbilstošā ēka -	300+	Patēriņš kopā	216.30			No atjaunojamiem energoresursiem ēkā sarabotā vai iegūtā enerģija	0.00			Kogenerācijā sarabotā enerģija	0.00			Primārās enerģijas novērtējums	281.60			Oglekļa dioksīda emisijas novērtējums	56.69				kg CO ₂ /m ² gadā
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8. Ēkas energosertifikāta izdevējs																																																									
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Reģistrācijas numurs	EA3-0012																																																								
Datums ³	Paraksts ³																																																								

Piezīmes: ¹ Ēku energoefektivitātes klase saskaņā ar ēkas patēriņa novērtējumu apkurei.

² Ēkas patēriņa novērtējums apkurei, kWh/m² gadā.

³ Dokumenta rekvizītus "Datums" un "Paraksts" neizpilda, ja dokuments sagatavots atbilstoši normatīvajiem aktiem par elektronisko dokumentu noformēšanu.

9. Ēkas norobežozošo konstrukciju īpatnējais siltuma zudumu koeficients				H_T/A_{ext} 0.00 W/(m ² K)				
				H_{Tn}/A_{ext} 0.00 W/(m ² K)				
<i>H_T un H_{Tn} - faktiskais un normatīvais ēkas norobežozošo konstrukciju siltuma zudumu koeficients, kas aprēķināts saskaņā ar normatīvajiem aktiem būvniecības jomā</i>								
10. Ēkas ventilācijas īpatnējais siltuma zudumu koeficients				H_{ve}/A_{ext} 0.00 W/(m ² K)				
<i>H_{ve} - faktiskais ēkas ventilācijas siltuma zudumu koeficients, kas aprēķināts saskaņā ar ēkas energoefektivitātes aprēķina metodi</i>								
Ventilācijas siltuma zudumu atgūšana apkures periodā				0.00%				
11. Energijas uzskaitē un sadalījums apkures un karstā ūdens sistēmās								
Kalendāra gads vai periods (no-ldz)	Energonesējs			Apkurei		Karstā ūdens apgādei		
	nosaukums	uzskaitītais daudzums		kWh	klimate korekcija kWh ⁵	kWh/m ² gadā	kWh	kWh/m ² gadā
		*	kWh					
2016	Centralizētā apkure	425050.00 kWh	425050.00	351922.00	382722.00	161.26	73128.00	33.51
2015	Centralizētā apkure	378370.00 kWh	378370.00	305818.00	373982.00	140.14	72552.00	33.25
2014	Centralizētā apkure	429040.00 kWh	429040.00	353536.00	396345.00	162.00	75504.00	34.60
2013	Centralizētā apkure	434770.00 kWh	434770.00	360082.00	368431.00	165.00	74688.00	34.22
2012	Centralizētā apkure	495440.00 kWh	495440.00	413216.00	456236.00	189.35	82224.00	37.68
<i>Piezīmes.</i>								
⁴ Dati par faktiski uzskaitītajiem energonesējiem par pēdējiem pieciem gadiem vai sezonām faktiski uzskaitītajās mērvienībās (t, m ³ , Mj, kcal vai cita).								
⁵ Klimata korekcijas koeficients attiecīgajai apkures sezonai patērīna normalizēšanai uz normatīvo apkures grādu dienu skaitu.								
12. Pielikumi un pievienotie dokumenti (dokumenta nosaukums, datums, numurs un lapu skaits)								
1) Pārskats par ekonomiski pamatotiem energoefektivitāti uzlabojošiem pasākumiem (bis-eed-1-2017-235-p.pdf)								
2) Pārskats par ekonomiski pamatotiem energoefektivitāti uzlabojošiem pasākumiem, kuru īstenošanas izmaksas ir rentablas paredzamajā (plānotajā) kalpošanas laikā (pielikums-parskats-par-pasakumiem-kristapa-18.pdf)								
3) Aprēķinos izmantotie ievaddati (pielikums-ievaddati-kristapa-18.pdf)								
13. Neatkarīga eksperta apliecinājums								
<i>Apliecinu, ka ēkas energosertifikāts sastādīts, nepieļaujot rīcību, kas manis paša, pasūtītāja vai citas personas interesēs varētu mazināt iegūto rezultātu pareizību, novērtējuma objektivitāti un ticamību.</i>								
Vārds uzvārds: Artūrs Biedris								
Reģistrācijas numurs: EA3-0012				Paraksts ⁶		Datums ⁶		
<i>Piezīme.</i> ⁶ Dokumenta rekvizītus "paraksts" un "datums" neaizpilda, ja dokuments sagatavots atbilstoši normatīvajiem aktiem par elektronisko dokumentu noformēšanu.								

Kristapa 18 “after renovation” Energy Performance Certificate (EPC)

ĒKAS PAGAUDU ENERGOSERTIFIKĀTS

REGISTRĀCIJAS NUMURS *BIS-ĒED-2-2023-3865*
 DERĪGS LĪDZ *14.08.2026*

Ēkas energosertifikāta veids	Atjaunotas/pārbūvētas ēkas nodošana ekspluatācijā		
Objekta veids	Dzīvojamā ēka		
Ēkas veids	Daudzdzīvokļu ēkas		
Adrese	Rīga, Kristapa iela 18		
Ēkas daļa	-		
Kadastra apzīmējums	01000602021001		
Ēkas raksturojums			
Būves gads 1959		Pārbūves gads 2023	
Stāvu skaits	5 virszemes, 1 pazemes, [] mansards, [] jumta stāvs		
Kopējā platība	2757.76 m ²	References platība	2315.45 m ²
References tilpums	6251.72 m ³	Vidējais stāva augstums	2.70 m
Ēkas energosertifikāta pielietojuma veids(-i)	Pie ēkas nodošanas ekspluatācijā		
Energoefektivitātes novērtējuma veids	Aprēķinātais, pie nodošanas ekspluatācijā		
Ēkas energosertificēšanas noliks	Brīvprātīgi		
Ēkas energoefektivitātes novērtējums (kWh/m² gadā) un klase			
C	62	87	
Apkurei	↓	↓	Kopā
Ēkas primārās enerģijas novērtējums (kWh/m² gadā) un klase			
Primārā neatjaunojamā enerģija	↑	Primārā kopējā enerģija	
B	113	113	
Ēkas energoefektivitātes rādītāji kWh/m² gadā		Vērtējums par ēkas atbilstību normatīvo aktu prasībām	
Apkurei	62	A ¹	Ēkas atbilstība gandrīz nulles enerģijas ēkas prasībām
Karstā ūdens sagatavošanai	25	A ¹	
Mehāniskajai ventilācijai	0	-	Ir veikta ēkas rādītāju pārbaude, pamatojoties uz faktisko būvniecības rezultātu
Apgaismojumam	0	-	
Dzesēšanai	0	-	Oglekļa dioksīda emisijas novērtējums, t CO ₂ gadā
Kopā	87	A ¹	Oglekļa dioksīda emisijas novērtējums, kg CO ₂ /m ² gadā
Ēkas energosertifikāta izdevējs	Eksperts		PARAKSTS
	Gatis Žogla		
	Registrācijas numurs	EA3-0009	
	Datums	14.08.2023	

¹ Visiem ēkas energoefektivitātes novērtējuma rādītājiem norāda izmantoto novērtēšanas metodi: A - aprēķinātais rādītājs, I_p - izmērītais rādītājs pēc faktiskā enerģijas patēriņa bez korekcijas, I_n - izmērītais rādītājs, kas koriģēts normalizētam izmantojumam, N - noklusējuma standartvērtība.

Ēkas tehniskie rādītāji	
Ēkas ārējās virsmas laukums	2993.00 m ²
Ēkas formas faktors - ārējās virsmas un references platības attiecība	1.29
Kompaktuma faktors - ārējās virsmas un tilpuma attiecība	0.48
Ārējo norobežojošo konstrukciju vidējais svērtais siltuma caurlaidības koeficients U_{ext}	0.39 W/(m ² K)
Ārējo norobežojošo konstrukciju vidējais svērtais normatīvais (maksimālais) siltuma caurlaidības koeficients $U_{ext,max}$	0.40 W/(m ² K)
Ēkas norobežojošo konstrukciju īpatnējais siltuma zudumu koeficients H_r/A_{ext}	0.51 W/(m ² K)
Ēkas norobežojošo konstrukciju pielaujamais īpatnējais siltuma zudumu koeficients $H_{tr,max}/A_{ext}$	0.53 W/(m ² K)
Aprēķina iekšējais apkures novērtējumam	21.0 °C
Aprēķina iekšējais dzesēšanas novērtējumam	0.0 °C
Pieprasītās gaisapmaiņas rādītājs	0.51 n ⁻¹
Ēkas ventilācijas īpatnējais siltuma zudumu koeficients H_{v}/A_{ext}	0.47 W/(m ² K)
Ventilācijas siltuma zudumu atgūšana apkures periodā	0.00 %
Ēkas gaisa caurlaidības testa rādītājs q_{30}	0.00 m ³ /(m ² h)
Ēkas sagatavošanas metode testa veikšanai	

Novērtējumā izmantotie primārās enerģijas faktori un CO ₂ koeficienti					
Enerģijas patēriņa pakalpojums	Energonešējs un efektivitātes koeficients	CO ₂ emisijas faktors, kg CO ₂ /MWh	Primārās enerģijas faktors		
			neatjaunojamo energoresursu daļai	atjaunojamo energoresursu daļai	kopējais
Apkure	Siltumenerģija no centralizētās siltumapgādes sistēmas, saražota no fosilajiem kurināmiem bez kogenerācijas [2]	264.00	1.30	0.00	1.30
Karstā ūdens sagatavošana	Siltumenerģija no centralizētās siltumapgādes sistēmas, saražota no fosilajiem kurināmiem bez kogenerācijas [2]	264.00	1.30	0.00	1.30
Ventilācija	-	-	-	-	-
Apgaismojums	-	-	-	-	-
Dzesēšana	-	-	-	-	-

Pielikumi un pievienotie dokumenti (dokumenta nosaukums, datums, numurs un lapu skaits)			
1) Aprēķinos izmantotie ievaddati (pielikums_ievaddati_Kristapa_18.docx)			
NEATKARĪGA EKSPERTA APLIECINĀJUMS			
Apliecinu, ka ēkas energosertifikāts sastādīts, nepielaujot rīcību, kas manis paša, pasūtītāja vai citas personas interesēs varētu mazināt iegūto rezultātu pareizību, novērtējuma objektivitāti un ticamību.			
Ēkas energosertifikāta izdevējs	Eksperts	Gatis Žogla	PARAKSTS
	Reģistrācijas numurs	EA3-0009	
	Datums	14.08.2023	

8.2. Annex 2

Social Acceptance Questionnaire Template by ICONS

Q1. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 indicates 'strongly disagree' and 5 indicates 'strongly agree,' please, rate the following statements: [KPI1.SA]

"I contribute to conserving energy by practicing habits such as turning off lights when not in use, unplugging electronics, and reducing unnecessary energy consumption."

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

"Utilizing alternative sources of energy, such as solar or wind power, can significantly reduce our reliance on traditional energy sources, like fossil fuels. By harnessing renewable resources, we can decrease our carbon footprint, mitigate environmental impact, and promote a more sustainable energy future."

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

"By reusing items, recycling materials, and minimizing waste generation, not only helps preserve natural resources and protect the environment but also promotes safe energy practices. By reducing the need for energy-intensive manufacturing processes we can conserve energy resources, minimize pollution, and create a safer and more sustainable energy ecosystem for future generations."

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

Q2. Are you aware of the ongoing interventions of the SUPERSHINE project? [KPI2.SA]

1. I have never heard about the project interventions.
2. I have heard about the project interventions, but I do not know much about them.
3. I have some understanding of the project interventions and their objectives.
4. I am well-informed about the project interventions and the benefits they bring to the community.
5. I am highly knowledgeable about the project interventions, especially the benefits they bring to the community.

D1.3 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 1

Q3. To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as being worth the investment made in your community? [KPI3.SA]

1. I believe the project interventions are not justified by the investment made.
2. I have doubts about whether the project interventions justify the investment.
3. I think the project interventions somewhat justify the investment.
4. I believe the project interventions strongly justify the investment.
5. I am highly convinced that the project interventions greatly justify the investment made.

Q4. To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices? [KPI4.SA]

1. The project interventions do not contribute to promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices at all.
2. The project interventions have a minimal impact on promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices.
3. I am unsure about the effectiveness of the project interventions in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices.
4. The project interventions effectively promote sustainable energy solutions and practices.
5. The project interventions significantly and successfully promote sustainable energy solutions and practices.

Q5. To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as beneficial to your overall quality of life, considering both the building experience and access to green or communal areas? [KPI5.SA]

1. The interventions do not have a positive impact on my quality of life, neither in the building nor in access to green areas.
2. The interventions provide minimal benefits to my quality of life, with limited improvement in the building experience and access to green areas.
3. I am undecided about the extent to which the interventions benefit my quality of life, as I do not notice significant changes in the building experience or access to green areas.
4. The interventions moderately improve my quality of life, with noticeable enhancements in both the building experience and access to green areas.
5. The interventions significantly enhance my quality of life, greatly improving both the building experience and access to green areas.

Q6. To what extent do you perceive the deployed technologies, such as control panels and thermostats, as user-friendly and easy to operate? [KPI6.SA]

1. The deployed technologies are extremely difficult to use and operate.
2. The deployed technologies are somewhat challenging to use and operate.
3. I am not sure about the ease of use of the deployed technologies.
4. The deployed technologies are fairly easy to use and operate.
5. The deployed technologies are extremely user-friendly and easy to operate.

Q7. How do you perceive the social image projected by the community? [KPI7.SA]

D1.3 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 1

1. The community projects a very poor social image.
2. The community's social image is generally poor.
3. I am undecided about the social image projected by the community.
4. The community projects a generally good social image.
5. The community projects a very positive social image.

Q8. What is your perception on the aesthetics of the buildings? [KPI8.SA]

1. I find the aesthetics of the building very unappealing.
2. I have negative perceptions of the aesthetics of the building.
3. I am undecided about the aesthetics of the building.
4. I find the aesthetics of the building appealing.
5. I find the aesthetics of the building very appealing.

Q9. How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during both winter and summer? [KPI9.SA]

Winter:

1. I am very uncomfortable with the temperature in my home during winter.
2. I am generally uncomfortable with the temperature in my home during winter.
3. I have mixed feelings about the temperature comfort in my home during winter.
4. I am generally comfortable with the temperature in my home during winter.
5. I am very comfortable with the temperature in my home during winter.

Summer:

1. I am very uncomfortable with the temperature in my home during summer.
2. I am generally uncomfortable with the temperature in my home during summer.
3. I have mixed feelings about the temperature comfort in my home during summer.
4. I am generally comfortable with the temperature in my home during summer.
5. I am very comfortable with the temperature in my home during summer.

Q10. Do you believe that the project interventions can contribute to reduce your energy bills? [KPI10.SA]

1. I do not believe that the project interventions can contribute to reduce my energy bill at all.
2. I believe that the project interventions can have a minimal impact on reducing my energy bill.
3. I am unsure whether the project interventions can contribute to reduce my energy bill.
4. I believe that the project interventions can somewhat contribute to reducing my energy bill.
5. I strongly believe that the project interventions can significantly contribute to reducing my energy bill.

Q11. To what extent do you feel integrated as part of the community as a result of the project interventions? [KPI11.SA]

1. I do not feel integrated as part of the community through the project interventions.
2. I feel only slightly integrated as part of the community through the project interventions.
3. I am undecided about feeling integrated as part of the community through the project interventions.

D1.3 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 1

4. I feel somewhat integrated as part of the community through the project interventions.
5. I feel fully integrated as part of the community through the project interventions.

Q12. How frequently do you utilize the green spaces within the community? [KPI12.SA]

1. I never use them or go there.
2. I rarely use them or go there.
3. I sometimes use or go to the green spaces.
4. I use and go to the green spaces often.
5. I use and go to the green spaces very often.

